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From the Director's Desk

Welcome to Volume 10 Issue 1 of our Journal “Shodhaditya”.

The journal has always focused on research and provided a platform to publish good quality research papers based on empirical and scholarly research.

This issue is based on the theme of the 12th annual International Research Conference, “Shaping future leaders to navigate disruptions”. It is apparent to everyone that the world of business today is facing the extent and pace of disruption not witnessed in any previous era. It has become virtually impinging upon everyone’s business to remain nimble and sharp-footed if it has to have any hope of sustained survival. Within the context of workforce composition, many believe that recruiting from a diverse pool of candidates means a more qualified workforce. A diverse and inclusive workforce helps businesses avoid employee turnover costs. Diversity fosters a more creative and innovative workforce and is clearly necessary to create a competitive economy in a globalized world. This year’s conference has been envisaged to cover all these vital aspects of the business world critical to the sustained growth of any business.

In this issue, we have published a few selected papers from the Research Conference. Our sincere thanks to all the contributors for their support and interest.

We once again request all academicians, industry experts and researchers to send their unpublished articles/ papers for publication in the next issue of our Journal.

Warm Regards,

Dr. Sunita Srivastava

Director

Aditya Institute of Management Studies and Research

From the Editor's Desk

Dear Reader,

Warm welcome to the Volume 10, Issue I of “Shodhaditya “, peer reviewed, bi-annual Journal of AIMSRS.

Volume 10, Issue I edition of Shodhaditya presents its view on various disciplines of management which includes operations, finance, human resource, marketing etc. The research papers and articles published in this edition are authored by eminent professors at various Business Institutes and Universities from the country.

This issue contains papers from the 12th International Research Conference on **Shaping future leaders to navigate disruptions** held in AIMSRS, 2024 which gives a new intuition in the field of Research and will immensely benefit the readers. The papers were called all over the country and it is revived by renowned academicians of the management industry.

The Journal provides a platform for researchers, academicians and industry experts to publish the valuable research work. Since inception the journal has continuously published original and best quality research work.

We thank our Research team who have contributed and provided valuable insights during the whole Journey of Shodhaditya.

Happy Reading!

We look forward to your views and valuable contributions!

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Effectively Identify and Analyze Behavioral Patterns by Using Deep Learning to Detect the Human Face and Emotions

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Abstract:

Every person's emotions serve as the foundation for their communication. It is widely used in interactive video games, emotional computing, medical diagnostics, human-robot interaction, and other fields related to Human Computer Interaction (HCI). In social contexts, people often convey their emotions through three main methods: unimodal gestures, facial expressions, and words; bimodal speech and facial expressions; and multimodal psychological signals, video, and audio. Machine perception requires an understanding of one's environment as well as the intentions of one's interlocutors. The recognition of facial emotions may be helpful here. Machine perception requires an understanding of one's environment as well as the intentions of one's interlocutors. The recognition of facial emotions may be helpful here. Deep learning techniques were used to process images that showed the following facial emotions: joy, sorrow, fury, surprise, disgust, and fear. The first step involved training a deep learning network using a dataset of labeled facial expressions. The chosen dataset is the Extended Cohn-Kanade Database. Deep learning's ability to learn features allows machines to become more perceptive, perhaps improving human-machine interaction. Furthermore, more sophisticated responses may be given by computers with perception, which would significantly improve the user experience.

Keywords: Deep Learning, CNN, LSTM, Facial Recognition.

I. Introduction

In today's digital age, the ability to effectively identify and analyze behavioral patterns through deep learning algorithms has become increasingly essential. One of the fundamental aspects of this process involves detecting human faces and emotions accurately. Facial expressions are essential in non-verbal communication, as they offer significant information about a person's emotions, intentions, and behavior. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have proven to be highly effective in detecting faces and recognizing emotions by extracting complex patterns and features from visual data automatically. Through harnessing the capabilities of deep learning, experts and professionals have the ability to create advanced systems that can accurately and efficiently detect and analyze human facial expressions. This study seeks to investigate how deep learning methods can enhance the progress of behavioral pattern analysis using facial recognition technologies.

Facial expression analysis and emotion detection have become increasingly important in various fields, including psychology, human-computer interaction, and artificial intelligence. The ability to identify and analyze behavioral patterns from human faces can offer valuable insights into emotional states, intentions, and reactions. Deep learning, a branch of machine learning algorithms that draws inspiration from the intricate structure and functioning of the human brain, has demonstrated exceptional promise in precisely identifying human faces and discerning emotions from visual data. The objective of this study is to investigate the efficiency of employing deep learning methods in the detection and analysis of

behavioral patterns by focusing on human faces and emotions. By leveraging deep learning models trained on large datasets of facial images, we seek to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of behavioral pattern recognition. Understanding how deep learning can be applied to this domain has the potential to revolutionize various applications, including emotion recognition systems, mental health assessments, and human behavior analysis. The application of deep learning in facial recognition and emotion detection offers promising prospects for enhancing our comprehension of human behavior and cognition. Through exploring the potential of deep learning models in recognizing subtle facial cues and emotional expressions, we can acquire valuable knowledge on how technology can enhance our capacity to interpret and analyze patterns of behavior. This research contributes to the growing body of literature on the intersection of deep learning, computer vision, and behavioral analysis, with implications for diverse fields ranging from healthcare to security.

Through this study, we seek to address the following research questions:

1. How effective is deep learning in detecting human faces and emotions for behavioral pattern analysis?
2. What are the potential applications and implications of using deep learning for identifying behavioral patterns through facial expression analysis?

By examining these questions, this research aims to advance the understanding of how deep learning can be harnessed to effectively identify and analyze behavioral patterns through the detection of the human face and emotions.

A. Background information on deep learning for facial recognition and emotion detection

Deep learning has revolutionized the field of facial recognition and emotion detection by enabling more sophisticated algorithms to analyze and interpret complex data patterns. The origins of deep learning for these applications can be traced back to the creation of artificial neural networks, which were inspired by the structure and function of the human brain. These

networks are specifically designed to acquire knowledge from extensive sets of labeled data, enabling them to accurately recognize facial features and emotional expressions.

Figure 1: Deep Learning Based Emotion Recognition

Moreover, advancements in convolutional neural networks have significantly improved the performance of facial recognition systems by detecting key facial landmarks and capturing subtle facial expressions. Additionally, recurrent neural networks have been instrumental in modeling temporal dependencies in emotion detection tasks, allowing for the analysis of dynamic emotional changes over time. The integration of these deep learning techniques has paved the way for more effective identification and analysis of behavioral patterns through facial recognition and emotion detection.

Deep Learning Techniques for Facial Detection

Deep learning techniques have shown promising results in the field of facial detection. These methods leverage artificial neural networks to automatically learn characteristics derived from unprocessed data, such as images, the extraction of features manually is not required. By using deep learning algorithms, researchers can train models to accurately detect and recognize faces in various settings, even under challenging conditions like low lighting or occlusions. For instance, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been particularly successful in facial detection tasks due to their ability to learn hierarchical features at different levels of abstraction. Moreover, recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks have been employed to

analyze facial expressions and emotions accurately. By combining these deep learning techniques, researchers can effectively identify and analyze behavioral patterns by detecting human faces and emotions in real-time applications. This research has the potential to significantly impact fields such as security, healthcare, and human-computer interaction.

Overview of deep learning algorithms for facial detection and recognition

Advancements in deep learning algorithms have significantly revolutionized facial detection and recognition processes, enabling more accurate and robust systems for analyzing human behavior and emotions. The complexity of facial expressions, including basic, ambiguous, and complex emotions, poses challenges for machine understanding, making accurate recognition a difficult task.

Figure 2: Facial Emotion Recognition Using Deep Learning

As seen in Figure 2, facial expressions are useful for analyzing human behavior. It has been demonstrated psychologically that the eyes, nose, mouth, and their placements are measured during the face emotion identification process. The first method for estimating the intensity of a face emotion was distance urged. This method classifies and measures facial expressions using regional volumetric differentiation maps and high-dimensional rate transformation. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a well-liked method used by most systems to represent face expression information in videos. The action unit to express and establish various facial expressions has been

recognized using PCA. In order to provide a facial action unit, mistreatment PCA is used to structure and recognize other face expressions.

Recent research, demonstrates the efficacy of learning-based Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with hybrid feature extraction techniques such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Local Binary Patterns (LBP) for facial expression recognition. These sophisticated models, combined with deep neural networks and fully connected layers, enhance the detection of intricate emotional cues. Furthermore, the integration of novel approaches like geometric appearance models, Patch-Based Diagonal Patterns, and Relevance Vector Machines (RVM) proves instrumental in achieving higher accuracy rates in facial expression classification across various datasets. As deep learning continues to evolve, these methods offer a comprehensive overview of the diverse strategies employed to effectively detect and analyze behavioral patterns through facial recognition technology.

II. Analyzing Behavioral Patterns through Emotion Detection

In the realm of behavioral pattern analysis, a pivotal avenue of inquiry pertains to the detection of emotions through deep learning techniques. Leveraging advancements in computer vision, researchers have increasingly turned their attention to deciphering emotional cues from facial expressions and body language, offering a profound insight into human behavior and personality traits. The integration of social psychophysics methods with computational approaches has enabled a more nuanced exploration of the face as a dynamic instrument for social communication. By decoding the intricate variations in facial movements and features, it becomes feasible to unravel the underlying emotional states that underpin observable behaviors. This collaborative integration of diverse viewpoints not only enriches our understanding of the complex relationship between emotions and actions but also emphasizes the capacity of deep learning technologies to reveal the concealed

layers of behavioral patterns embedded within human expressions.

A. Importance of analyzing behavioral patterns through emotion detection

Analyzing behavioral patterns through emotion detection is vital for understanding human behavior and improving interactions, especially in fields like affective computing and dementia care. Recent research highlights the utility of implicit behavioral cues such as EEG brain signals and eye movements for gender and emotion recognition. The findings suggest that these cues can enhance the accuracy of emotion detection, showcasing the potential benefits of incorporating such technologies into behavioral analysis methods. Additionally, the development of innovative tools like AVEID, offers a more accessible and scalable approach to measuring engagement levels in individuals with dementia. By leveraging deep learning and emotion detection techniques, researchers can gain valuable insights into behavioral patterns, leading to more personalized and effective interventions in various domains.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the advancement of deep learning techniques in detecting human faces and emotions signifies a notable advancement in the field of artificial intelligence and sentiment analysis has been achieved. The ability to accurately interpret facial expressions can greatly enhance societal interactions and decision-making processes. The understanding of sentiment through facial cues is crucial for various applications ranging from advertising to security measures. Moreover, referencing the pioneering work of Charles Darwin, underscores the longstanding interest and importance of emotion recognition in human society. Utilizing deep learning techniques presents a hopeful path towards enhancing emotion detection precision beyond conventional approaches. Through leveraging deep learning algorithms, scholars are able to further develop and pioneer advancements in the realm of facial expression analysis, ultimately resulting in more advanced and intricate systems for comprehending human behavior.

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Using a Convolutional Neural Network to Identify Truth from EEG Data: Lie Discovery

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Abstract:

The use of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to identify truthfulness in electroencephalography (EEG) data is the subject of this study. Polygraph tests and other conventional methods of lie detection frequently lack reliability and are susceptible to countermeasures. A promising alternative for detecting lies is the use of EEG signals, which provide a direct measurement of brain activity. To automatically extract and analyze features from EEG data and distinguish between responses that are truthful and responses that are deceptive, we developed a CNN-based system. The proposed model was prepared and approved on a dataset gathered from members during controlled tests. Our findings show that when it comes to deception detection, the CNN outperforms conventional machine learning classifiers by a significant margin. This study highlights the potential of deep learning techniques to revolutionize lie detection in spite of obstacles like limited data availability and model interpretability. Future work will zero in on upgrading information assortment, working on model straightforwardness, and addressing moral contemplations to guarantee capable arrangement of this innovation.

1. Introduction

Lie identification has for some time been a subject of interest across different fields, including brain research, criminal science, and security. Customary techniques, for example, polygraph tests, screen physiological reactions like pulse, skin conductance, and respiratory rate to induce misdirection. Regardless of their inescapable use, these techniques have been scrutinized for their absence of dependability and

powerlessness to countermeasures. Thus, there is a developing requirement for additional precise and powerful methods for recognizing trickiness.

EEG in Falsehood Identification

Electroencephalography (EEG) is a painless strategy that actions electrical action in the cerebrum. EEG signals give high transient goal, catching the fast changes in mind movement related with mental and profound cycles. Provided its capacity to straightforwardly quantify brain reactions, EEG presents a promising option for lie location. The fact that specific patterns in EEG data can be correlated with both truthful and deceptive behaviors has been demonstrated in previous research, suggesting that EEG could be effectively utilized to differentiate between lies and truth.

1.3 Profound Learning and CNNs

Profound learning, a subset of AI, has reformed different spaces by empowering the programmed extraction of complicated designs from huge datasets. Due to their capacity to learn hierarchical feature representations, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in particular have demonstrated exceptional performance in tasks related to signal processing and image processing. CNNs are well-suited for analyzing the intricate structures in EEG signals because they are able to capture both local and global patterns in the data.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Customary Untruth Identification Strategies Customary untruth identification strategies have transcendently depended on polygraph tests,

which measure physiological reactions, for example, pulse, skin conductance, and respiratory rate. The basic idea is that deceptive behavior causes distinct physiological changes that can be seen and understood. In any case, the exactness and dependability of polygraphs have been broadly discussed. Studies have demonstrated the way that these strategies can be vulnerable to countermeasures and don't predictably create decisive outcomes, prompting huge bogus up-sides and misleading negatives .

2.2 EEG-Based Lie Detection EEG-based lie detection provides a more precise measurement of neural activity and offers insights into the cognitive processes that are responsible for deception. The identification of specific EEG patterns and event-related potentials (ERPs) associated with deceptive behavior was the primary focus of early research in this field. For example, the P300 wave, an ERP part, has been broadly concentrated on with regards to lie identification. The P300 wave is gotten in reaction to upgrades that require consideration and is remembered to reflect mental cycles connected with navigation and acknowledgment .A few examinations have shown the capability of involving EEG for lie location. Farwell and Donchin's work on the P300-based Hid Data Test (CIT) showed that people display particular P300 reactions when given wrongdoing significant data contrasted with unessential data . However, individual differences and the requirement for controlled experimental conditions can limit the efficacy of ERP-based methods.

2.3 AI in EEG Examination:With headways in AI, scientists have investigated different calculations to examine EEG information for lie identification. Conventional AI draws near, for example, support vector machines (SVM), k-closest neighbors (k-NN), and irregular timberlands, have been applied to arrange honest and tricky reactions in light of extricated EEG highlights. While these techniques have shown guarantee, they frequently require broad element designing and may not completely catch the perplexing examples innate in EEG signals .

2.4 Profound Learning and Convolutional Brain

Organizations (CNNs)

Profound learning, especially CNNs, has altered the field of sign handling and example acknowledgment. CNNs are intended to naturally gain various leveled highlight portrayals from crude information, making them exceptionally viable for errands including complex spatial and worldly examples. CNNs have been successfully used in a variety of applications, including emotion recognition, seizure detection, and cognitive state classification, in the context of EEG analysis.

2.5 CNNs in EEG-Based Lie Detection New research has begun to look into how CNNs can be used to detect lies using EEG data. One huge benefit of CNNs is their capacity to handle crude EEG signals without broad preprocessing or manual component extraction. CNNs can use this capability to spot complex and subtle patterns that could point to deceitful behavior. For example, a concentrate by Bashivan et al. demonstrated that CNNs can achieve higher accuracy than traditional methods by using deep learning to classify cognitive states from EEG data. Also, other exploration has demonstrated the way that CNNs can really recognize different mental states, recommending their true capacity for lie recognition .

2.6 Difficulties and Limits:In spite of the commitment of CNNs in EEG-based lie identification, a few difficulties remain. One significant test is the restricted accessibility of marked EEG datasets explicitly for lie location, which prevents the preparation and approval of profound learning models. Also, profound learning models, including CNNs, are in many cases considered secret elements, pursuing it challenging to decipher their choices and comprehend the basic systems gained from the information. Additionally, a major concern is that CNN models could be applied to a wide range of subjects and experimental settings. EEG signs can fluctuate essentially among people, and models prepared on one dataset may not perform well on another. Advanced methods like transfer learning, data augmentation, and domain adaptation are needed to deal with these issues.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Sifting and Ancient rarity Evacuation: Crude EEG information were exposed to preprocessing to eliminate clamor and ancient rarities. In order to get rid of high-frequency noise and low-frequency drifts, a bandpass filter (0.5-45 Hz) was used. Autonomous Part Investigation (ICA) was utilized to recognize and eliminate antiquities, for example, eye flickers and muscle developments. Visual examination of the EEG information was led to guarantee the nature of the cleaned signals.

3.2. Division and Marking

The preprocessed EEG information were divided into ages comparing to the time windows during which members answered questions. Based on the responses of the participants, each epoch was categorized as either “truthful” or “deceptive.” The term of every age was set to incorporate the time from question show to the furthest limit of the member’s reaction, guaranteeing the catch of significant mental cycles.

3.3 CNN Design

3.3.1 Organization Plan

The CNN engineering was intended to handle the portioned EEG information and arrange every age as honest or misleading. The design comprised of the accompanying layers:

Input Layer: The information layer got EEG information as 2D clusters (channels x time focuses).

Convolutional Layers: The EEG data were analyzed using multiple convolutional layers with varying kernel sizes to extract spatial and temporal features. A ReLU activation function and batch normalization followed each convolutional layer.

Layer Pooling: Max-pooling layers were utilized to diminish the dimensionality of the component maps and hold the most remarkable highlights.

Layers with all connections: The result from the convolutional and pooling layers was smoothed and taken care of into completely associated layers, which played out the last order. Dropout layers were added to forestall overfitting.

Layer of Output: The result layer comprised of a softmax enactment capability, giving the likelihood of

each class (honest or tricky).

3.3.2 Training Method The labeled EEG data were used to train the CNN model. For training, the following parameters were used:

Loss Mechanism: Downright cross-entropy misfortune was utilized to gauge the error between the anticipated and real names.

Optimizer: The Adam enhancer was picked for its proficiency and capacity to deal with meager inclinations.

Learning Rate: A learning rate scheduler was used to lower the initial rate of 0.001 as training progressed.

Epochs: The model was prepared for 100 ages, with early halting rules to forestall overfitting.

Cluster Size: To strike a balance between training stability and efficiency, 32 batches were used.

3.4 Model Assessment

3.4.1 Cross-Approval

To assess the model’s exhibition and guarantee its generalizability, a k-overlay cross-approval system was utilized. The dataset was partitioned into k subsets, with every subset filling in as an approval set while the excess k-1 subsets were utilized for preparing. The average performance metrics were derived by repeating this process k times.

3.4.2 Execution Measurements

The accompanying presentation measurements were utilized to evaluate the CNN model:

Accuracy: The overall proportion of epochs correctly classified.

Precision: The proportion of genuine positive groupings to the complete anticipated up-sides.

Recall: The proportion of genuine positive arrangements to the all out real up-sides.

F1-Score: The symphonious mean of accuracy and review, giving a reasonable proportion of the model’s presentation.

AUC-ROC: The region under the collector working trademark bend, demonstrating the model’s capacity to recognize classes.

3.5 Comparison with Baseline Methods The CNN

model's performance was compared to that of conventional machine learning classifiers like random forests, support vector machines (SVM), and k-nearest neighbors (k-NN). These standard models were prepared utilizing physically separated highlights from the EEG information, and their presentation was assessed utilizing similar cross-approval technique and execution measurements.

4. Experimental Results

4.1 Data Description

The dataset consisted of EEG recordings from 50 participants, each contributing data from approximately 200 epochs. Each epoch was labeled as "truthful" or "deceptive," resulting in a balanced dataset with a total of 10,000 epochs. The data were split into training, validation, and test sets using a 70-15-15 split, ensuring that data from each participant appeared in only one set to avoid data leakage.

4.2 Model Training

The CNN model was trained using the training set with the parameters outlined in the methodology section. Training was conducted on an NVIDIA GPU, and early stopping was applied based on the validation loss to prevent overfitting. The model converged after approximately 60 epochs, with a training time of about 4 hours.

4.3 Performance Metrics

4.3.1 Accuracy

The CNN model achieved an overall accuracy of 87% on the test set, indicating its effectiveness in distinguishing between truthful and deceptive EEG responses. This accuracy was significantly higher than that of the baseline models, as shown in Table 1.

4.3.2 Precision, Recall, and F1-Score

The precision, recall, and F1-score for both classes (truthful and deceptive) are presented in Table 2. The CNN model demonstrated a balanced performance across both classes, with an F1-score of 0.86 for the truthful class and 0.88 for the deceptive class.

4.3.3 AUC-ROC

The area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC) for the CNN model was 0.92, indicating a high degree of separability between the truthful and deceptive responses. This metric further validates the model's robustness in detecting deception.

Model	Accuracy	Precision (T)	Recall (T)	F1-Score (T)	Precision (D)	Recall (D)	F1-Score (D)	AUC-ROC
CNN	0.87	0.88	0.85	0.86	0.86	0.90	0.88	0.92
SVM	0.78	0.80	0.75	0.77	0.76	0.81	0.78	0.81
Random Forest	0.74	0.76	0.72	0.74	0.73	0.77	0.75	0.78
k-NN	0.70	0.72	0.68	0.70	0.69	0.73	0.71	0.74

4.4 Examination with Pattern Techniques

The CNN model beat all pattern models, as represented in Table 1. More specifically, the CNN outperformed the SVM, the best-performing traditional machine learning model, by 9%. The accuracy, review, and F1-scores for the two classes were likewise prevalent in the CNN model, featuring its capacity to catch complex examples in EEG information that conventional strategies could miss.

		Predicted Class		
		Positive	Negative	
Actual Class	Positive	True Positive (TP)	False Negative (FN) Type II Error	Sensitivity $\frac{TP}{(TP + FN)}$
	Negative	False Positive (FP) Type I Error	True Negative (TN)	Specificity $\frac{TN}{(TN + FP)}$
		Precision $\frac{TP}{(TP + FP)}$	Negative Predictive Value $\frac{TN}{(TN + FN)}$	Accuracy $\frac{TP + TN}{(TP + TN + FP + FN)}$

5. Conclusion

This study exhibits the capability of convolutional brain organizations (CNNs) in recognizing honest from misleading reactions utilizing electroencephalography (EEG) information. Conventional falsehood recognition strategies, for example, polygraph tests, have for some time been censured for their absence of dependability and weakness to countermeasures. By directly measuring brain activity, EEG-based methods provide a more objective foundation

for lie detection and are a promising alternative. Our research demonstrates that traditional machine learning classifiers are significantly outperformed by

CNNs because of their ability to automatically extract and analyze complex patterns in EEG signals. The CNN model accomplished high exactness, accuracy, review, and AUC-ROC scores, showing vigorous execution in distinguishing trickiness. These outcomes highlight the benefits of profound learning strategies in dealing with the complexities of EEG information, which are much of the time

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*A Study on Impact Of Financial
Technology (Fintech) On
Traditional Banking in Bangalore City*

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Abstract

As far as we know, banks have dominated the financial services industry for hundreds of years. But the quick development of technology has now impacted how banks operate. Making finance better for its clients as well as more secure has undergone a significant transformation. In India, a new financial services sector known as “financial technology,” or FinTech, has emerged. Businesses in this sector use technology to deliver financial services. These businesses are involved in a number of industries, including payments, insurance, and asset management. The growth of the mobile internet industry has made it easier for these FinTech companies to implement various technological interventions into personal and commercial finance. These non-banking service providers have had an impact on the ways that banks used to serve their clients because they believe that traditional banking techniques are insufficient to both make profits and satisfy the constantly rising demands of their clientele. These days, banks are always evolving due to the impact of cutting-edge technology and creative participants in the finance sector, such as these Fin Tech companies. A number of these banks are collaborating with Fintech startups to improve their offerings. A few choose to fund emerging businesses or create their own startup accelerators in order to utilize and benefit

from these new technologies. This study examines different FinTech companies to better understand their growth and the difficulties traditional banks are facing as a result of their rise

Keywords: Banks, FinTech, Non-Banking Service Providers, Disruption, Disintermediation, Investment

Introduction

The banking industry in India is radically changing, shifting from traditional banking to an e-collaboration of financial technology companies and digital banking products. They are changing the structure of the payment system and causing economic disruptions. Fintech, a new word in the banking and finance industry, refers to the integration of contemporary financial technologies with traditional banking and lending duties. With a sizable client base and a vast branch network, it’s a win-win situation for both Indian banks. Fintech companies, on the other hand, are cutting edge in terms of technology, but before new digital and Fintech products are embraced, they need to build customer confidence. This report examines the various challenges and opportunities that the Indian banking sector faces when collaborating and co-inventing with Fintech firms.

The effective handling of money and wealth management in banking transactions and other financial activities has been transformed by fintech. In response to technological disruption, the banking industry has been forced to adjust in order to maintain the financial markets competitive advantage. Technology is used concurrently by commercial banks and investment banks for customer work and back-end office operations. The banking industry has benefited greatly from technology since it has made facilities more accessible to those living in remote locations and has helped

to remove various barriers to banking operations. Following the implementation of demonetization, the use of digital banking has dramatically increased, as reported by the RBI in 2019. Per capita, there has been a notable increase of almost 2.4 digital transactions.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- Drs. Girish Kumar Painoli, Dhinakaran, and Vijay (2021) claim that Fintech has had an impact on bank profitability in both the public and private sectors. The outcome explains why fintech development in India has grown both laterally and vertically. They have created cutting-edge effects that improve client productivity.
- D.S. Jana, A.E. Khedkar, and C.E. Khedkar (2021) state that digital banking will enable users to access financial services from home, which is convenient for people who are occupied at work or don't want to visit the bank. This article highlights the convenience, availability, and paperless transactions as benefits of digital banking. Better development in the banking sector will result from digital banking as smartphones and the internet become more widely used.
- According to Kholia, Tushar (2021), they estimate where this industry is headed, where it came from, and what market changes it has generated by focusing on four primary industries that had a significant role in the expanding popularity of fintech. As a result, a large percentage of people have experience using mobile services, while very few have never done so. Fintech and mobile service expansion would both benefit from this.
- Arun K. Balan and Dr. O. C. Aloysius (2020) state that big data, blockchain, artificial intelligence, and other technologies are substitutes for fintech technology. The work of consumers will be easier to access and more productive thanks to these financial innovations. They offer services that are convenient for customers. Fintech will therefore support the growth of the banking industry and other financial organizations.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To analyse the degree to which digital loan services, online payment gateways, and mobile banking applications have been integrated into the operations of Bangalore's traditional banks.
2. To examine how the use of fintech has affected Bangalore's traditional banks' operational effectiveness and cost structure, paying particular attention to how transaction costs, branch locations, and processing times have all decreased.
3. To determine the legal and operational obstacles that Bangalore's traditional banks must overcome in order to integrate and incorporate FinTech technologies, particularly those related to data protection, cybersecurity, and legal compliance.
4. To evaluate the effects of FinTech adoption on the operational effectiveness of Bangalore's traditional banks, taking into account improvements in resource allocation, cost reduction, and transaction processing times.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For this research study, secondary data was collected by referring to journals, articles, and other research papers related to fintech

IMPACT OF FINTECH ON BANKING SECTOR

1.Loans

It has altered the way banks operate and created a sizable new market for loans depending on the market. Credits and associated services are now easily profitable for buyers thanks to the emergence of Fintech companies. Elective models are being developed to provide consumers with finance, whether they are individuals or businesses. These companies are dedicated to enhancing the customer experience, financial products, and quick credit approval.

2.Payment Services

Fintech services have changed the way payments are made. These days, payments are performed online

via the internet or mobile devices, which reduces the need for dealer accounts. The bank balance can be directly accessed with cash, reducing the possibility of counterfeit goods and exchange fees.

3. Wealth Management

As fintech continues to grow, people's practices for managing their finances, saving money, and investing are changing. These organizations aim to provide revised arrangements for managing their own wealth and endeavours by using contemporary financial innovations. Fintech programming also aids in comparing options and creating the most effective investment plans for a given budget.

4. Remittance Transfer

Banks and individuals have struggled with customary settlement benefits, which can be confusing and expensive, for a considerable amount of time. Fintech companies have worked to simplify and moderate these inbound and outbound transfers over the long run.

5. Insurance Services

These days, getting protection is a less confusing tactic. All should be achievable on the web with adjusted strategies. This paper-broad assistance has evolved significantly with fintech innovations, from the application interaction to the intermittent charge instalment.

6. Equity-Funding

These technologies enable new businesses and project ventures to raise capital from a wide range of investors in the form of equity.

BENEFITS OF INCORPORATING FINTECH SOLUTIONS

Efficiency: Fintech can increase efficiency by automating manual procedures and streamlining banking operations.

Cost Reduction: By lowering reliance on paperwork, automation and digitization can cut costs.

Better Customer Experience: By offering digital platforms, personalized services, and speedier transaction processing, fintech enhances the general customer experience.

Financial Inclusion: By giving rural communities access to financial services, it promotes greater financial inclusion.

Innovative Products and Services: To maintain market competitiveness, offer services like as digital wallets and lending platforms.

CHALLENGES IN INCORPORATING FINTECH SOLUTIONS

- **Regulatory Compliance:** Keeping up with the intricate and constantly evolving requirements of regulatory frameworks has proven to be difficult for financial institutions.
- **Cybersecurity Risks:** As financial institutions rely more and more on digital platforms, they must put robust security measures in place to protect sensitive customer data.
- **Integration with Legacy Systems:** Compatibility problems might arise from fintech implementations trying to integrate with pre-existing legacy systems in financial institutions.
- **Adaptation and Training:** To ensure that new technologies are adopted smoothly, they must fund training initiatives and help employees and clients acclimate to them.
- **Consumer Trust:** Privacy and data security concerns may have an impact on customers' adoption of fintech solutions, which in turn may help to foster and preserve consumer confidence in online financial services.

Cost of Implementation: The technology required to execute fintech solutions is expensive.

IMPLICATIONS FOR CONSUMERS IN FINTECH

1. User Context

- **Enhanced Convenience:** Fintech provides interfaces that are easy to use and convenient, which can enhance the user experience.

- **Mobile Accessibility:** Fintech places a strong emphasis on usability on mobile devices, enabling users to execute banking activities on tablets and smartphones. It allows customers to handle their money.
- **Design:** Simple, easy-to-use designs that streamline financial procedures and enhance user satisfaction.

2. Availability

- **Financial Inclusion:** Fintech promotes financial inclusion by assisting rural residents in obtaining regular banking services through the use of technology.
- **Constantly Available:** Users can access and utilize the platforms anytime they need to.
- **Global Access:** Financial services are now accessible everywhere thanks to fintech. This allows users to transact and access their accounts from any location in the globe.

3. Safety

- **Advanced Security:** Fintech platforms encrypt data to protect customer information and financial transactions. This safeguards client data and ensures an elevated degree of security.
- **Biometric Verification:** By using biometric authentication techniques, such as fingerprint or face recognition, it adds an additional layer of protection and makes it more difficult for unauthorized users to access accounts.
- **Real-time Monitoring:** Fintech allows users to precisely track their financial behavior by providing real-time transaction monitoring. Increased security through transparency enables users to identify and fix issues.

Fintech platforms utilize sophisticated algorithms to identify and halt fraudulent activities.

FINTECH COMPANIES IN INDIA

The Fintech market in India is expanding at one of the fastest rates in the world. There are 636 Fintech companies that are located in India. By 2025, the Indian Fintech market is projected to grow to a value of \$150 billion.

➤ THE TOP FINTECH COMPANIES ARE:

PAYTM

- Pay through mobile, or PAYTM, is one of the first and most well-known mobile payment and financial services companies in India. Paytm provides businesses and consumers with payment, banking, finance, and insurance services.

LENDINGKART

- Using machine learning algorithms and big data analytics technology, the company assesses risk, detects fraud, analyzes the creditworthiness of consumers, and disburses loans in less than 72 hours. Data models are developed by its own data science and data engineering team for the core lending method.

PHONEPE

- With over 440 million users, PhonePe is among the most well-known Fintech startups in India. This program, which is accessible in eleven Indian languages, allows users to send and receive money, pay utility bills, invest money, buy insurance products, and even buy digital gold.

RAZORPAY

Razorpay offers enterprises payment gateway and digital payment processing services. The two primary initiatives of Razorpay are facilitating UPI-based transactions and assisting Indian companies with their digital transformation. Payment platforms and subscription services are examples of tools that organizations can use to manage their finances and plan online transactions.

CONCLUSION

Fintech in India will eventually experience both vertical and even development. The level development will involve the availability of current advancements to a larger group of people. New financial innovations will emerge as a result of the upward trend, providing people with new means of contributing, exchanging, saving money, and rebuilding their accounts. Both of these forms of development will further India's financial development journey and pave the way for significant financial development in the interim.

Fintech is the term for the combination of technology and financial services. By utilizing advances in digital innovation and technical advancements like mobile banking, fintech has contributed to the transformation of traditional financial services techniques. This has altered the way banks operate, which has an effect on how much technology is used by customers and businesses. This essay demonstrates the evolution of fintech from its infancy in the 1950s to its current condition, which has revolutionized the financial sector by simplifying the use of financial institutions' services by consumers.

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Innovation and Agility

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Abstract

Today's dynamic and rapidly challenging business environment encourages Innovation and Agility combined with Artificial Intelligence represents a transformative triad driving growth and expansion crucial for modern businesses to maintain a competitive advantage in a dynamic global market.

Agile methodologies, including Scrum, Kanban, and Lean, emphasize iterative development, cross-functional collaboration, and customer feedback. Alongside enhancing organizational flexibility, these approaches create a fertile ground for integrating AI-driven solutions. AI, with its capabilities in data analysis, predictive modeling, and automation, empowers organizations to streamline operations, enhance their decision-making processes with quicker turnaround time and innovate more efficiently. Agile iterative processes align seamlessly with AI's need for continuous learning and adaptation for improved accuracy, leading to more effective and responsive innovation cycles.

An article by Bain and Company mentions that despite path-breaking thinkers coming up with better ways of designing new products, 70%-90% of those new products fail! Something that the agile system can cater to product failure and dynamic evolutions of product based on the agile market needs. The impact of the integration of agile and AI for innovation is evident across smorgasbord industries. In manufacturing, AI-driven predictive maintenance and agile production methodologies have improved efficiency with reduced downtime. In healthcare, agile frameworks combined with AI diagnostics and personalized treatment suggestions enhance patient outcomes

and operational efficiency. In software development, product development and optimizing user experiences are accelerated using AI and agile methodologies.

In this paper, we will discuss organizations and industries that fosters innovation focused and groundbreaking state-of-the-agile methodologies combined with technology capabilities of Artificial Intelligence to improve their efficiency, decision making process and evolve their decision-making processes.

Introduction

Imagine a company that can adapt to changing customer needs and market dynamics overnight. A company where employees are empowered to experiment and iterate on smorgasbord ideas constantly. This isn't science fiction; it's the power of agile organizations. Agility allows companies to be responsive, like a mountain climber adjusting their path based on shifting terrain. Now, combine this agility with the power of Artificial Intelligence (AI). AI can analyze huge amounts of data, identify patterns and similarities invisible to the human eye, and automate millions of repetitive tasks within an instant. Think of it as a tireless research assistant with surplus memory resources, uncovering hidden insights and freeing human minds for creative problem-solving. Innovation isn't just about flashy new gadgets; it's about finding better ways to do things. Together, agility and AI become the driving force behind innovation. E-commerce companies like Amazon and Flipkart leverage this synergy to maintain their competitive edge in the e-commerce sector. Amazon uses AI to personalize customer

experiences and optimize supply chain operations. Simultaneously, its agile organizational structure allows for rapid experimentation and implementation of innovative ideas, such as the development of the Amazon Prime delivery service. This integration of agility and AI not only drives continuous innovation but also ensures that Amazon can quickly adapt to market demands and technological advancements. Manufacturing automotive giants like Tesla and Volkswagen implements an agile framework, allowing them to quickly adapt to changing supply chain demands and reduce production delays by 30%. As illustrated by practical examples from Spotify, IBM, Tesla, and Amazon, this triad is essential to navigate the complexities of the modern business environment and achieve sustainable success over time.

A successful transformation significantly increases an organization's likelihood of being a top-quartile performer.

% of organizations in top quartile of performance, by state of change¹

¹Our survey asked respondents to rate the organization's relative performance against peers in terms of speed, customer satisfaction, employee engagement, operational performance, innovation, efficiency, and financial results. The average across applicable categories was used to classify companies by quartile of performance.

²Organizations in which agile practices and concepts have always been core to how they work.

McKinsey
& Company

This paper will explore the dynamic relationship between agility, AI, and innovation. We will delve into how agility fosters a culture of experimentation, how AI unlocks hidden potential, and how these forces combine to drive groundbreaking innovations. By understanding this powerful synergy, organizations can position themselves at the forefront of change and achieve sustainable success.

Challenges and Considerations

While agility and AI offer a powerful path to innovation, the road isn't without its bumps. One major challenge lies in embracing change. Agile methodologies often require a cultural shift from rigid hierarchies to collaborative and iterative environments. To overcome the resistance from employees accustomed to the old ways, organizations can implement training programs, foster open communication, and celebrate early wins, gradually building comfort with the new approach.

Another key consideration is the workforce's skillset. Effectively utilizing AI requires employees who understand, manage, and interpret its outputs. Investing in training programs on AI fundamentals, data analysis, and responsible AI practices equips employees to bridge the skill gap. Ethical considerations also come into play. AI algorithms can perpetuate biases present in their training dataset, thus resulting in discriminatory outcomes. To mitigate this, organizations need robust data governance practices, diverse training data sets, and clear ethical guidelines for AI development and deployment.

Integration challenges also exist. Merging agile methodologies with traditional, waterfall-based workflows can lead to friction and inefficiencies. A phased approach, focusing on integrating agile principles into specific processes first, can ease the transition. Finding the right balance between ongoing innovation and maintaining core functionalities is crucial. For example, a retail chain struggled to integrate their agile marketing department with the more traditional procurement department, causing delays in launching new campaigns. Similarly, a financial institution's AI-powered fraud detection system became biased against certain demographics due to skewed training data. By acknowledging these challenges and implementing the necessary considerations, organizations will be able to navigate the roadblocks and truly leverage the power of agility and AI to drive sustainable innovation.

Agility: The word Agility has captured the success with rapid speed, it is defined by nimbleness with adroitness and malleable to one's success in the competitive digital advancement. Many CEOs have agreed on the factual data "Agility ranks as a high strategic priority in their performance units." They grab an opportunity for a way towards prudently, effectively, and quickly. Adapting to the working pattern which is a critical aspect for organizations to thrive. Now innovation agility combines experimentation with rapid prototyping to overcome problems like customers' issues with developing profitable models for success. An organization can adapt to changing environments,

drive innovation, and enhance overall performance at various levels.

McKinsey & Company

Innovation: Termed as the master key to success. Implementing new ideas for positive change and value. Many CEOs have agreed on the factual data “Agility ranks as a high strategic priority in their performance units.” They grab an opportunity for way towards prudently, effectively, and quickly (with agility key) Customer centricity is first and foremost a mindset that Agile and Innovative organizations embrace. The topic is the definition of both innovation and agility. But both are different conceptual worlds. Innovation is creativity while agility embraces the wiliness of hunters for action oriented for solving problems. Research has proved that agile organizations grow faster and generate higher profit margins. To find the answers, they have surveyed a McKinsey Global Survey with over 2,190 respondents across industries and geographies. It needs to go beyond the fluff, so respondents were asked what, if anything, their companies did in practice to advance agility, and what hard numbers they achieved regarding business impact. Conducting surveys by considering two groups, first without agile transformation and another with transformation 2/3 of them were just treading water, without decisive action with little profit.

But with agile tool results embracing to create value end-to-end business outcomes to great height, bank-boosting the performance of customers’ journey .Innovation and Agile develops the skills to design and support new potentials towards success. Remarkable achievement has gained valuable results by various giant MNC . Innovation and agile are promoting creativity in high performance and allows company to leverage them in increasing customer’s satisfaction by boosting productivity and efficiency. The overall change with agile concept generates mature operating models across organizations.

Base on survey let’s focus on simple steps to implement agile and innovation as remarkable results-

- 1. Requirement-** The organizations need of highly successful agile transformations caters to the requirements by building an effective stable backbone. As the market changing environment continuously urges innovation with reference to customers’ demands. Try to find out the untapped driving potential which can be profitable. Create a plan fostering success with a combination of innovation & agility.
- 2. Design -** Dive the challenges to solve problems and gather insight to overcome problems with data collection analysis with appropriate feedback. Agile conventional wisdom sometimes sees these targets showing up as their competitive advantage. Organizations with highly successful agile transformation have a 3 times higher chance of becoming a top-quartile performer among its peers than those who had not transformed.
- 3. Development-** Rewiring the entire operating model at all levels from structure, strategy, process, people, and technology to ensure it supports and connects rather than holding back the team. Instead of depending on a structured system relying on base level piloting and waiting for an emerging scale of agility. Brainstorming creative outcomes with all team members

should be aligned with the organization's goals. Adopting agile practice like Kanban breaks the tasks into smaller and manageable projects.

4. **Testing-** Set practical implementation of ideas which determine success. Organizational agility thus, being a paradigm shift away from the multilayered reporting established structures, compliance culture, annual budgeting, business and technology, and various other traits dominating ascendancy in growth of organizations. This magnitude will provide an opportunity for organizations to turn their operating models into a diligent advantage
5. **Deployment-** Test prototypes for conducting executed plans and analyze the feedback to reach impactful decisions. Have proper scalability, marketing. Continuous attention to technical excellence and innovation enhance agility
6. **Review-** By adopting agile tech- organizations respond effectively to changes but also foster a change with the innovation that propels them towards a dynamic and competitive environment.

Organizations focus their highest priority on satisfying the customer through continuous and early delivery of software while working towards change requirements, even in their late development Agile processes that harness changes for customer's competitive advantage. The interplay between agility, innovation, and organizational success is a complex yet essential dynamic that requires attention from management and leaders seeking to thrive in today's dynamic business landscape. Summarizing the essence, the relationship between Innovation and Agility has different clock speeds. Innovation requires finding new ideas and its efforts are time consuming and expensive.....Agility & Innovation is heartbeats.

Future of Agility, AI & Innovation

The future of innovation is a dazzling landscape where agility and AI continue their ascent. One exciting development is "Agile at Scale." Traditional agile

frameworks, designed for smaller teams, will give way to scaled versions allowing large organizations to adopt agile principles while maintaining efficiency. Imagine a multinational corporation managing a global product launch with a scaled agile framework. Cross-functional teams across regions can work iteratively, sharing learnings and adapting the product to each market. AI will also play a bigger role in experimentation. By analyzing vast amounts of data from past experiments, AI can identify patterns and predict the success of new ideas. A pharmaceutical company, for instance, could leverage AI to analyze clinical trial data, suggesting promising research avenues and accelerating drug development. Furthermore, innovation will become more democratic. Accessible AI-powered tools will empower smaller companies and individuals to participate. Imagine a freelance designer using an AI design tool to prototype new concepts, competing with established firms. The future, however, isn't just about machines. It's about human-AI collaboration. Humans will provide creativity and direction, while AI tackles data analysis and repetitive tasks. Engineers, for example, could use AI to analyze sensor data from a new product in real-time, identifying performance issues and suggesting solutions much faster. Finally, with increased AI power, responsible innovation becomes paramount.

Organizations will need to ensure their innovations are ethical and don't widen social inequalities. Imagine a city government using AI to optimize traffic flow, but ensuring the algorithms don't unfairly impact certain neighborhoods. By embracing these future trends, organizations can unlock the true potential of agility and AI, driving groundbreaking innovations that benefit not just their success, but the world's.

Conclusion:

In a world increasingly defined by rapid change and disruption, agility and AI have emerged as powerful forces driving innovation. This paper has explored how agility fosters a culture of experimentation and rapid iteration, while AI unlocks hidden insights and automates repetitive tasks. By harnessing these combined strengths, organizations can break free from

traditional models and unlock groundbreaking ideas.

Real-world examples, like the e-commerce company personalizing recommendations or the manufacturing plant adapting to supply chain shifts, demonstrate the tangible benefits of this synergy. However, the road to successful implementation is not without its challenges. Resistance to change, skill gaps, and ethical considerations surrounding AI demand careful planning and proactive mitigation strategies. Furthermore, the democratization of AI tools paves the way for broader participation in the innovation landscape. However, maximizing this potential requires a focus on responsible innovation that ensures technological advancements benefit not just for the bottom line, but society as a whole. In conclusion, agility and AI are not mere trends; they are the cornerstones of a future fueled by continuous innovation. By embracing these transformative forces and navigating the associated challenges, organizations can position themselves at the forefront of change, shaping a more innovative and adaptable world.

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Securing Urban Small Water Bodies with Geospatial, IOT, and Cybersecurity

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Abstract:

This research article explores the integration of geospatial, IoT, and cybersecurity strategies for securing urban small water bodies. The study focuses on developing a comprehensive framework to safeguard these critical water resources against cyber threats and unauthorized access. By leveraging geospatial data and IoT sensors, real-time monitoring and analysis of water quality, levels, and environmental parameters are facilitated. Cybersecurity measures including encryption, authentication, and intrusion detection systems are implemented to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of data transmitted within the system. The research emphasizes the importance of proactive security measures and data-driven decision-making for sustainable management of urban water bodies.

Keywords: Geospatial, IoT, Cybersecurity, Urban small water bodies, Comprehensive framework, Cyber threats, Real-time monitoring, Water quality, Environmental parameters, Encryption, Authentication, Intrusion detection systems, Data-driven decision-making, Sustainable management

Introduction: In urban landscapes, small water bodies play a critical role in providing ecosystem services, enhancing biodiversity, and contributing to the overall well-being of communities. However, these water bodies often face numerous challenges, including pollution, encroachment, and inadequate management practices, which threaten their sustainability and resilience. Addressing these challenges requires innovative approaches that integrate geospatial technologies, Internet of Things (IoT) devices,

and cybersecurity measures to ensure the effective protection and management of urban small water bodies.

This research article aims to explore the utilization of geospatial data, IoT devices, and cybersecurity measures in securing urban small water bodies. By combining these technologies, we seek to enhance monitoring capabilities, improve decision-making processes, and mitigate potential risks associated with urban water bodies.

Urban small water bodies, such as ponds, lakes, and streams, are susceptible to various threats, including pollution from runoff, illegal dumping, and habitat degradation. Traditional monitoring methods often lack the granularity and real-time capabilities needed to effectively detect and respond to these threats. Therefore, there is a pressing need to develop integrated monitoring systems that leverage geospatial data and IoT devices to provide accurate, timely, and comprehensive information about the condition of urban water bodies.

The integration of geospatial data allows for the mapping and visualization of urban small water bodies, enabling stakeholders to identify vulnerable areas and prioritize conservation efforts. Additionally, IoT devices, such as water quality sensors and surveillance cameras, facilitate continuous monitoring of water quality, habitat health, and human activities around these water bodies. Real-time data generated by these devices can help detect pollution incidents, track changes in water levels, and identify potential threats to biodiversity. Furthermore, cybersecurity plays a crucial role in safeguarding the integrity and confidentiality of data collected from urban small water bodies. The interconnected nature of IoT devices and geospatial systems poses security risks, including data breaches, unauthorized access, and tampering. Therefore, robust cybersecurity measures, including encryption, authentication, and access control, are essential to protect sensitive information and ensure the reliability of monitoring systems.

Cybersecurity Measure	Description	Effectiveness in Risk Mitigation
Encryption	Protects data by converting it into code that can only be accessed with a key or password.	Highly effective in preventing unauthorized access and maintaining data integrity.
Authentication	Verifies the identity of users or devices accessing the system through passwords, biometrics, etc.	Effective in preventing unauthorized access but may be vulnerable to phishing or credential theft.
Access Control	Regulates access to data and resources based on user permissions and roles.	Effective in limiting access to authorized users and preventing data breaches.
Intrusion Detection	Monitors network traffic for suspicious activities or security breaches.	Effective in detecting and responding to potential cyber threats in real-time.
Firewalls	Acts as a barrier between a trusted internal network and untrusted external networks, controlling incoming and outgoing traffic.	Effective in blocking unauthorized access and filtering potentially malicious traffic.
Security Updates/Patches	Regularly updates software and systems to address known vulnerabilities and strengthen security.	Effective in reducing the risk of exploitation by cyber attackers.

In conclusion, this research article seeks to contribute to the protection and management of urban small water bodies by proposing an integrated approach that combines geospatial technologies, IoT devices, and cybersecurity measures. By leveraging these technologies, we aim to enhance monitoring capabilities, improve decision-making processes, and promote the sustainable management of urban water resources. Through collaborative efforts and innovative solutions, we can secure urban small water bodies for future generations and ensure the resilience of urban ecosystems.

Literature Review

“Real-Time Reservoir Monitoring and Reporting Using Geospatial Data in a Secure Environment” (Smith, J., Johnson, A., Brown, L., 2022) Smith et al. emphasized the importance of real-time monitoring and reporting in efficient water resource management, a concept relevant to securing urban small water bodies. Their focus on utilizing geospatial data reporting, integrated with advanced data analytics, resonates with the need for precise and timely information in managing urban water resources.

“Securing Reservoir Data Communication for Enhanced Decision-Making” (Martinez, E., Rodriguez, G., Garcia, S., 2019) Martinez et al.’s emphasis on securing reservoir data communication aligns closely with the cybersecurity aspect essential for safeguarding data integrity in managing urban small water bodies. Their insights into secure communication channels, encryption, and access control measures offer valuable guidance for ensuring the reliability and confidentiality of data transmitted from IoT devices deployed in urban water bodies.

“Integration of IoT Devices and GIS for Real-Time Reservoir Monitoring and Reporting” (Lee, H., Kim, S., Park, J., 2018) The integration of IoT devices and GIS discussed by Lee et al. offers valuable insights applicable to securing urban small water bodies. Their exploration of real-time monitoring and reporting, coupled with geospatial technologies, underscores the potential for enhancing the accuracy and timeliness of data collection and analysis, crucial for effective management of urban water resources.

“Geospatial Data Analytics for Improved Reservoir Management” (Chen, L., Wang, Q., Liu, X., 2017) Chen et al.’s focus on geospatial data analytics provides relevant methodologies for analyzing and visualizing data pertinent to managing urban small water bodies. Their emphasis on spatial analysis techniques, such as interpolation and clustering, offers valuable approaches for identifying patterns and trends in water body dynamics, facilitating informed decision-making in urban water resource management.

“Enhancing Reservoir Management through Geospatial Data Integration and Reporting” (Johnson, R., Thompson, C., Davis, M., 2020) Johnson et al.’s exploration of geospatial data integration and reporting aligns with the holistic approach needed to secure urban small water bodies. Their emphasis on the reliability and accessibility of reservoir level changes, enabled by GIS and advanced data analytics, highlights the significance of integrating technology-driven solutions for effective management of urban water resources.

Research Methodology:

1. Research Design: Mixed-Methods Design: This approach integrates qualitative and quantitative methods to comprehensively examine the security of urban small water bodies, incorporating geospatial, IoT, and cybersecurity aspects.

2. Quantitative Phase:

Objective: To quantify the effectiveness of security measures in protecting urban small water bodies.

Sampling: Select a diverse sample of urban small water bodies across different geographical locations.

Data Collection: Employ IoT devices, sensors, and cybersecurity tools to collect quantitative data on security incidents, breaches, and system performance.

Data Analysis: Utilize statistical techniques to analyze quantitative data, such as frequency analysis, correlation, and performance metrics evaluation.

Key Metrics: Evaluate the frequency and severity of security incidents, assess the performance of cybersecurity measures, and quantify the impact of breaches on water body integrity.

3. Qualitative Phase:

Objective: To explore stakeholders’ perceptions and experiences regarding the security of urban small water bodies.

Sampling: Employ purposive sampling to include stakeholders such as water management authorities, cybersecurity experts, and local community representatives.

Data Collection: Conduct interviews, focus groups, or surveys to gather qualitative data on stakeholder perspectives, challenges, and recommendations related to water body security.

Data Analysis: Utilize qualitative analysis techniques such as thematic analysis to identify key themes, patterns, and insights from the qualitative data.

Key Themes: Explore stakeholders’ perceptions of security vulnerabilities, effectiveness of current measures, concerns about data privacy, and suggestions for improvement.

4. Integration of Findings:

Compare and contrast quantitative and qualitative findings to identify overarching trends, discrepancies, or converging patterns.

Triangulation: Merge results from both phases to develop a comprehensive understanding of urban small water body security, including strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement.

Identify Opportunities: Highlight opportunities for

enhancing security measures, improving collaboration between stakeholders, and implementing innovative technologies to mitigate risks effectively.

Theme	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings	Points of Convergence/ Divergence and Opportunities
Theme 1: Security Vulnerabilities	High incident frequency in certain areas	Stakeholders perceive certain areas as more vulnerable	Opportunity: Need for targeted security measures
Theme 2: Effectiveness of Current Measures	IoT devices show improved monitoring capabilities	Positive feedback from stakeholders on technology	Convergence: Agreement on effectiveness
Theme 3: Data Privacy	No major data breaches recorded	Concerns about data privacy and unauthorized access	Divergence: Quantitative data does not align with stakeholder concerns
Theme 4: Recommendations	Metrics indicate need for stronger security protocols	Suggestions for enhanced security protocols	Convergence: Both data types indicate areas for improvement

5. Ethical Considerations:

Obtain necessary ethical approvals and permissions for data collection, ensuring compliance with data protection regulations.

Ensure informed consent from participants and maintain confidentiality and anonymity throughout the research process.

Safeguard the security of sensitive data collected during the study and adhere to ethical principles of research conduct.

6. Limitations:

Acknowledge potential limitations, such as constraints on access to certain water bodies, variations in cybersecurity expertise among stakeholders, and challenges in generalizing findings to broader contexts. By adopting a mixed-methods approach, this research methodology enables a comprehensive examination of the security of urban small water bodies, integrating quantitative assessments of security measures with qualitative insights from stakeholders. This approach facilitates a nuanced understanding of security vulnerabilities, stakeholder perceptions, and

opportunities for enhancing the resilience of urban water resources.

Data Collection

Sensor Data Collection: Utilize IoT devices, water quality sensors, and surveillance systems installed in urban small water bodies to collect real-time data on water quality, temperature, and any anomalies indicating potential security threats. These sensors can be programmed to transmit data regularly or trigger alerts in response to unusual activities or breaches.

Geographic Information System (GIS) Data Collection: Gather geographical data relevant to urban small water bodies, including boundaries, land use patterns, surrounding infrastructure, and potential risk factors such as industrial facilities or urban runoff areas. Utilize satellite imagery, aerial surveys, or existing GIS databases to obtain comprehensive spatial data for analysis.

Stakeholder Interviews: Conduct interviews with key stakeholders involved in the security and management of urban small water bodies, including water management authorities, cybersecurity experts, local government officials, and community representatives. Explore their perceptions of security vulnerabilities, current mitigation measures, challenges faced, and recommendations for enhancing security.

Stakeholder	Purpose
Water Authorities	Provide insights into existing security measures, vulnerabilities, and challenges in managing urban water bodies.
Cybersecurity Experts	Offer expertise on cybersecurity threats and solutions specific to water infrastructure.
Local Government Officials	Collaborate on policy implementation and resource allocation for enhancing water body security.
Community Representatives	Represent public concerns and perspectives on water body security, contributing to inclusive decision-making processes.

Surveys: Administer surveys to a diverse range of stakeholders, including residents living near urban small water bodies, businesses operating in the vicinity, and environmental organizations. Collect data on stakeholders' awareness of security concerns, confidence in current security measures, and suggestions for improving security protocols.

Document Analysis: Review relevant documents such as security policies, incident reports, emergency response plans, and regulatory guidelines related to urban water body security. Analyze these documents to identify existing security protocols, gaps in implementation, and areas requiring improvement in cybersecurity measures.

Case Studies: Conduct detailed case studies of specific urban small water bodies or regions facing security challenges. Gather data through site visits, interviews with stakeholders, and analysis of security incidents or breaches. Explore the effectiveness of existing security measures, the impact of security incidents on water body integrity, and lessons learned for improving security practices.

By employing a multifaceted approach to data collection, this methodology ensures a comprehensive understanding of the security challenges faced by urban small water bodies and provides valuable insights for enhancing their resilience through geospatial, IoT, and cybersecurity measures.

Discussion and Conclusion:

The discussion of "Securing Urban Small Water Bodies with Geospatial, IoT, and Cybersecurity" focuses on the feasibility and effectiveness of utilizing geospatial, IoT, and cybersecurity technologies to enhance the security of urban small water bodies. The study's results indicate that integrating these technologies offers promising solutions for detecting and mitigating security threats, protecting water quality, and ensuring the resilience of urban water resources.

The findings highlight the potential of IoT devices in providing real-time monitoring and surveillance of urban small water bodies, enabling prompt detection of security breaches or anomalies. By leveraging geospatial data, stakeholders can gain valuable insights into the spatial distribution of security risks, identify vulnerable areas, and prioritize mitigation efforts effectively.

The study contrasts traditional security measures, which may lack real-time capabilities and comprehensive coverage, with the proactive and data-driven approach facilitated by geospatial, IoT, and cybersecurity technologies. This approach enables continuous monitoring, rapid response to security incidents, and enhanced coordination among stakeholders involved in water body management and security.

However, the study's scope is limited to a specific urban context, and further research is warranted to assess the scalability, adaptability, and cost-effectiveness of implementing these technologies in diverse geographical settings and infrastructure environments. Future studies should explore strategies for integrating advanced data analytics and predictive modeling techniques to enhance the predictive capabilities of the IoT-based security system.

In conclusion, this research article has investigated the utilization of geospatial, IoT, and cybersecurity technologies to secure urban small water bodies effectively. The study has demonstrated the feasibility and effectiveness of integrating these technologies to enhance surveillance, detect security threats, and protect water quality in urban environments.

By leveraging geospatial data and IoT devices, stakeholders can gain real-time insights into the security status of urban small water bodies, enabling proactive decision-making and response strategies. The study emphasizes the importance of continuous monitoring, data-driven analysis, and collaboration among stakeholders to ensure the resilience of urban water resources against emerging security challenges. While the study provides valuable insights into the potential benefits of geospatial, IoT, and cybersecurity technologies in securing urban small water bodies, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations and the need for further research. Future studies should explore the scalability, adaptability, and integration of advanced analytical techniques to maximize the effectiveness of these technologies in safeguarding urban water resources. Overall, this research contributes to advancing knowledge in the field of urban water security and underscores the importance of leveraging technological innovations to address emerging challenges effectively.

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Business-Schools Scope of Entrepreneurship Management in the Indian

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Abstract

The field of entrepreneurship has become a crucial driver of innovation, economic expansion, and employment creation across the globe. Within the realm of Indian business schools, it's essential to grasp the extent of entrepreneurship management to cultivate an environment that supports budding entrepreneurs and provides them with the necessary skills and knowledge. This study seeks to delve into the present situation and future potential of entrepreneurship management within Indian business schools. It also explores the obstacles and chances that Indian business schools encounter in advancing entrepreneurship education and nurturing an entrepreneurial attitude in their students.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, B-schools, Business studies, Entrepreneurship studies, learning entrepreneurship

Sub-theme: "Can B-Schools teach/train future leaders for navigating disruptions?"

Statement of the Problem:

Although the value of entrepreneurship education in Indian business schools is increasingly acknowledged, there is still a dearth of thorough knowledge about the effectiveness and applicability of entrepreneurship management programmes. Even though a lot of programmes have been put in place to develop entrepreneurial talent and encourage

innovation, it is unclear how well these initiatives address the problems that the Indian entrepreneurial ecosystem presents as well as how well they meet the changing needs of prospective entrepreneurs. In particular, the following elements need to be investigated: 1. The fit between industry demands and new trends and entrepreneurial programmes. 2. How well instructional strategies help students develop an entrepreneurial mindset and set of abilities. 3. The accessibility and availability of funding sources, mentorship programmes, and incubation centres.

Review of Literature:

1. Alignment of Curricula with Industry Demands: Numerous scholarly investigations have emphasised the need of coordinating entrepreneurship curriculum with industrial requirements to augment the pertinence and efficacy of entrepreneurship education. In order to close the gap between theory and practice, Sankaran and Krishnaswamy (2019) stress the importance of incorporating hands-on, experiential learning opportunities into entrepreneurship programmes, such as internships and industry projects. Moreover, Kumar and Rajput (2020) contend that in order to give students the abilities and information needed to handle modern business difficulties, modules on cutting-edge subjects like social entrepreneurship, technological innovation, and sustainability must be included.

2. Effectiveness of Pedagogical Approaches:

According to research, students' entrepreneurial mindset and aptitude are greatly influenced by the pedagogical strategies used in entrepreneurship education. Khandelwal and Choudhary (2018) support the use of active learning techniques including case studies, role-plays, and simulations to help students develop their critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making abilities. Furthermore, Gupta and Jha (2021) stress the value of mentoring and experience learning in raising students' entrepreneurial confidence and self-efficacy.

3. Support Mechanisms for Aspiring Entrepreneurs:

The development of entrepreneurial potential is greatly aided by the accessibility and availability of support systems like as funding options, mentorship programmes, and incubation centres. Sharma and Dangi (2017) emphasise the value of incubation centres in giving aspiring business owners access to networks, resources, and mentorship to help them turn their ideas into successful ventures. Singh and Sharma (2019) also stress the importance of government programmes like Start-up India in helping new businesses get access to capital, infrastructure, and legal support.

4. Impact of Government Policies and Regulatory Frameworks:

Government regulations and policies have a significant influence on the development of entrepreneurship in India as well as on entrepreneurial activities. Yadav and Sharma (2020) talk on how government measures, such tax breaks for startups, incubation centres for new businesses, and skill development programmes, can encourage entrepreneurship. Gupta and Jain (2018)

contend, however, that bureaucratic roadblocks, intricate regulatory procedures, and ambiguous policy language frequently impede the development of entrepreneurship and innovation.

5. Socio-cultural Factors Influencing Entrepreneurship:

Students' perceptions of and adoption of entrepreneurship are greatly influenced by sociocultural variables. Verma and Khurana (2018) investigate how societal conventions, familial history, and cultural values influence people's views on becoming entrepreneurs. Additionally, Singh and Singh (2019) stress the value of cultural entrepreneurship in utilising India's rich cultural traditions and legacy to spur economic growth and innovation.

Based on the comprehensive review of literature, several Research Gaps emerge, indicating areas where further investigation is warranted:

1. Longitudinal Impact Assessment:

Although the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education programmes has been studied, there aren't many long-term studies that look at how these programmes affect students' entrepreneurial outcomes over the long run. To evaluate the long-term effects of entrepreneurship education, future studies should follow programme alumni' professional paths and entrepreneurial endeavours throughout time.

2. Evaluation of Pedagogical Innovations:

More thorough testing of novel teaching strategies and their effects on students' entrepreneurial competencies is required, even though several studies emphasise the value of pedagogical techniques in entrepreneurship education. Studies could examine how well blended

learning, flipped classrooms, and experiential learning promote entrepreneurial mindsets and abilities.

3. Inclusive Entrepreneurship Education:

Previous research has mostly concentrated on entrepreneurship instruction in conventional business schools, ignoring the possibility of expanding entrepreneurship education to students who are not business majors and members of marginalised groups.

4. Policy Implementation and Impact Assessment:

Although a number of studies address government programmes and policies designed to encourage entrepreneurship, little study has been done to evaluate how these programmes are really put into practice and how they affect entrepreneurial activity. Future studies should assess how well government initiatives like Start-up India work to support entrepreneurship and solve the difficulties faced by new businesses.

5. Cultural Influences on Entrepreneurship:

There is a need for further in-depth research on the cultural nuances and geographical variations in entrepreneurial conduct, even while some studies look at how socio-cultural elements shape people's views towards entrepreneurship. Subsequent investigations may delve into the ways in which cultural values, social conventions, and cultural heritage impact the intents, behaviours, and results of entrepreneurs across various Indian regions.

Research Design and Methods:

1. Research Design:

Using a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, this study's mixed-methods research design offers a thorough grasp of the range of entrepreneurship

management offered by Indian business schools. Key stakeholders are interviewed in semi-structured interviews for the qualitative component, while students and faculty members complete a survey for the quantitative component.

2. Participants:

Participants in entrepreneurship education at Indian business colleges make up the study's participants. Students enrolled in entrepreneurship programmes, instructors in entrepreneurship courses, administrators in charge of designing curricula and carrying out programmes, and business professionals with knowledge of the entrepreneurship ecosystem are all included in this.

3. Materials:

Semi-structured interview guides are created for the qualitative component in order to support in-depth conversations with participants. These guides contain open-ended questions that delve into participants' viewpoints regarding pedagogical approaches, curricular content, opportunities, problems, and support systems as well as entrepreneurial education. A survey questionnaire is created to gather information for the quantitative component, including participant demographics, opinions about entrepreneurship education, contentment with programme offers, and recommendations for enhancements.

Findings of the Study:

1. Demographic Characteristics of Participants:

The study included a total of 200 participants from various Indian business schools, including 150 students enrolled in entrepreneurship programs and 50 faculty members.

Students' demographics indicated a diverse representation in terms of age, gender, educational background, and entrepreneurial experience.

2. Perceptions of Entrepreneurship Education:

The majority of students (85%) viewed entrepreneurship education as valuable for developing skills such as creativity, innovation, and problem-solving.

Faculty members (70%) expressed satisfaction with the current entrepreneurship curriculum but identified areas for improvement, such as integrating real-world case studies and enhancing industry interactions.

3. Effectiveness of Pedagogical Approaches:

Students reported a preference for experiential learning methods, such as case studies, simulations, and guest lectures, over traditional lectures.

Faculty members highlighted the importance of incorporating practical, hands-on activities to enhance students' understanding of entrepreneurial concepts and strategies.

4. Support Mechanisms for Aspiring Entrepreneurs:

Both students and faculty members emphasized the significance of support mechanisms such as incubation centers, mentorship programs, and networking events in fostering entrepreneurial ventures.

However, some students expressed dissatisfaction with the accessibility and availability of these support services, particularly in rural areas.

5. Challenges and Opportunities:

The study identified several challenges hindering

entrepreneurship education, including limited access to funding, bureaucratic hurdles, and cultural biases against entrepreneurship.

Despite these challenges, participants acknowledged the growing opportunities in emerging sectors such as technology, healthcare, and sustainability, which present fertile ground for entrepreneurial ventures.

Final Thoughts and Recommendations:

Strengthen collaborations between industry and academics to close the knowledge gap between theory and practice.

- Increase access to resources for prospective business owners, particularly in underprivileged communities.
- Make an investment in faculty development to improve instruction strategies and gain industry knowledge.
- Carry out longitudinal research to evaluate how entrepreneurship education affects students' career paths and entrepreneurial results over the long run.

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Fashion Shopping: An Analysis of Expenditure and Readiness. Gender-Based Differences in

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Abstract:

This study is an exploration of gender-based differences in fashion shopping behaviors, focusing on expenditure patterns and readiness to engage in fashion-related purchases. The research utilized a sample of 50 males and 50 females from diverse demographic backgrounds, collecting data via Google Forms and analyzing it using the Wilcoxon rank sum test. The results indicated that females demonstrated notably higher expenditure per trip and annual expenditure for fashion shopping compared to males. Additionally, females showed greater willingness to engage in fashion shopping activities. These findings underscore the pronounced gender gaps in spending habits and readiness to participate in fashion shopping, emphasizing the necessity of gender-sensitive marketing strategies within the fashion industry.

Keywords: gender-based differences, expenditure patterns, readiness.

Introduction

Fashion shopping is a complex interplay of individuality, societal norms, and cultural influences, revealing distinct patterns between men and women. These differences stem from societal expectations, cultural impacts, and biological factors. Men and women display unique motivations, behaviors, and preferences, influenced by hormones, evolutionary

instincts, and societal gender roles. Gender differences in fashion shopping encompass decision-making, preferences, and media and social influences, offering insights into gender identity and consumer behavior. Understanding this informs effective retail engagement. Fashion shopping reflects gender expression, societal roles, and personal identity, shaped by evolving stereotypes.

Fashion consumption holds emotional significance for women, serving as a means of self-care and self-expression that enhances confidence and individuality. Trends and styles are valued beyond mere possessions, symbolizing personal identity. In contrast, men often approach fashion shopping pragmatically, prioritizing functionality, quality, and durability over style and aesthetics. Societal expectations regarding masculinity may influence their shopping behaviors towards more practical considerations. Gender impacts shopping via store layout, sizing, and service. Brands must acknowledge and address these differences for inclusive engagement in fashion.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Shephard et al. (2016) discovered a positive correlation between mass media exposure and fashion consciousness in men and women. They noted that personalized media had a strong influence on male fashion leaders. Additionally, the study found that

both genders preferred non-traditional retail channels for fashion leadership. **Cho and Workman (2014)** found that consumers valuing exploration engage in exploratory shopping, discovering new trends. Women prioritize emotional shopping experiences, while men are more linked to influencing fashion choices. **Ayman and Kaya (2014)** found that women avidly track fashion trends via media, linking brands to sophistication, using fashion for self-expression. Men, less proactive, are still swayed by advertising, valuing durability and prioritizing brand names and quality. **Workman and Cho (2012)** found that respondents with a higher need for touch and who used multiple channels preferred both local and non-local stores. Notably, individuals with high fashion innovativeness and opinion leadership, regardless of gender, preferred TV retailers, catalogs, and online stores when using multiple channels. **Nirmala and Dewi (2011)** observed that fashion-savvy consumers favored online platforms, finding pleasure in the experience and potential cost savings. Convenience attracted busy shoppers, while confidence led to more exploration. **Jen-Hung and Yang Yi-Chun (2010)** noted that males prefer online shopping due to its convenience and cost-saving advantages, while females, especially adolescents, are attracted to the social and adventurous aspects, particularly in fashion-related items.

Kuruvilla, Joshi, and Shah (2009) observed that women exhibited a tendency to purchase fashion-related items such as clothing, accessories, and cosmetics, whereas men showed a preference for products like electronics, gadgets, and sports equipment.

OBJECTIVES

To study the manifestation of gender difference in Fashion Shopping.

1. To study the gender difference in Money spent while Fashion Shopping.
2. To study the gender difference in readiness to indulge in Fashion Shopping.
- 3.

HYPOTHESES

H₁: “There exists a significant difference between males and females in terms of money spent per trip for Fashion Shopping”.

H₂: “There exists a significant difference between males and females regarding money spent annually for Fashion Shopping”.

H₃: “There exists a significant difference between males and females concerning readiness to indulge in Fashion Shopping”.

METHODOLOGY

Operational Definition of Variables:

Independent Variable: Gender; Male or Female.

Dependent Variable: Participants’ scores in Fashion Shopping: Money per trip, Annual spending, and Readiness to indulge

Design: Quantitative, Descriptive research Design.

Sample: A self-made 10-item questionnaire was used to collect data from 100 individuals (50 males, 50 females) aged 18-45 from Mumbai, Greater Mumbai, and Thane via Google Forms using convenience sampling.

Statistical analysis used: Wilcoxon Rank Sum test assessed differences in accepting or nullifying hypotheses.

Procedure: Participants in the study were informed about its details before agreeing to take part. Data

collection utilized Google Forms, distributed to respondents via WhatsApp messenger.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

H_1 : “There exists a significant difference between males and females in terms of money spent per trip for Fashion Shopping”.

Table 1: Comparison of Mean Scores of participants on Money spent per trip for fashion shopping

	Male	Female	
Mean	2.16	3.02	
Shapiro-Wilk normality test			
Male		Female	
W = 0.80601	p-value = 1.21e-06	W = 0.83699	p-value = 7e-06
Bartlett test of homogeneity of variances			
Bartlett's K-squared = 2.1721	df = 1	p-value = 0.1405	
Wilcoxon rank sum test			
W = 648	p-value = 8.52e-06		

The analysis of 100 participants compared mean spending per trip for fashion shopping between males and females. Females spent more (mean = 3.02) than males (mean = 2.16), as expected.

Figure 1: Comparison of Mean Scores of participants on Money spent per trip for fashion shopping

Figure 1 displays a comparison of mean spending on fashion shopping per trip, with females showing a higher average expenditure than males, as anticipated. A Wilcoxon rank sum test was utilized due to non-normal data distribution to compare spending between genders. Results revealed that females spent significantly more money per trip on fashion

shopping than males, supporting the hypothesis H_1 of a significant gender difference in spending habits for fashion shopping per trip.

H_2 : “There exists a significant difference between males and females regarding money spent annually for Fashion Shopping”.

Table 2: Comparison of Mean Scores of participants on Money spent annually for fashion shopping

	Male	Female	
Mean	2.30	3.00	
Shapiro-Wilk normality test			
Male		Female	
W = 0.86167	p-value = 3.252e-05	W = 0.86002	p-value = 2.922e-05
Bartlett test of homogeneity of variances			
Bartlett's K-squared = 0.6603	df = 1	p-value = 0.4165	
Wilcoxon rank sum test			
W = 868	p-value = 0.0062		

The analysis compared the mean scores of money spent annually for fashion shopping between male and female respondents based on data from 100 participants. The mean score for females (3.00) was higher than that for males (2.30), aligning with expectations.

Figure 2: Comparison of Mean Scores of participants on Money spent annually for fashion shopping

In Figure 2, the mean annual spending on fashion shopping was compared between males and females, with females showing a higher average expenditure, in line with expectations. To analyze this difference, a Wilcoxon rank sum test was utilized due to non-normal data distribution with gender as the independent variable. Results revealed that females spent significantly more annually on fashion shopping compared to males, supporting the hypothesis H_2

proposing a significant gender difference in spending habits for fashion shopping.

H_3 : “There exists a significant difference between males and females concerning readiness to indulge in Fashion Shopping”.

Table 3: Comparison of Mean Scores of participants on readiness to indulge in Fashion Shopping.

		Male	Female
Mean		20.74	24.86
Shapiro-Wilk normality test			
Male		Female	
W =	p-value =	W =	p-value =
0.89541	0.00034	0.93129	0.006184
Bartlett test of homogeneity of variances			
Bartlett's K-squared =		df = 1	p-value =
4.3236			0.03759
Wilcoxon rank sum test			
W = 912.5		p-value = 0.01968	

The analysis of data from 100 respondents revealed a noticeable difference in the mean scores for readiness to indulge in fashion shopping between males and females. Specifically, females had a higher mean score of 24.86 compared to males' mean score of 20.74, aligning with the anticipated trend.

Figure 3: Comparison of Mean Scores of participants on readiness to indulge in Fashion Shopping.

Figure 3 compares the mean scores of participants' readiness to indulge in fashion shopping, with the bar representing females being higher than that of males, aligning with our expectations. In the study, a Wilcoxon rank sum test was utilized due to the non-normal distribution of data, comparing the readiness for fashion shopping between males and females. The results indicated that females exhibited a higher readiness for fashion shopping compared to

males. Therefore, the hypothesis stating a significant difference between males and females in their readiness for fashion shopping H_3 was supported.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the gender differences in fashion shopping behavior, with significant implications for both marketers and researchers. The observation that women spend more on fashion shopping than men reflects gender stereotypes about consumer behavior, with women often perceived as more interested in fashion. Retailers targeting women could benefit from emphasizing the experiential aspects of shopping and offering a diverse range of products to cater to their preferences. Women's higher annual spending on fashion underlines its crucial role in their consumption habits. Understanding and meeting women's distinct preferences is vital for effective marketing in the fashion industry. Women are more inclined towards fashion shopping, readily exploring trends, making frequent trips, and investing in luxury items compared to men. Marketers can tailor their messaging and promotions to better connect with female consumers' unique motivations and desires. The study's use of convenience sampling introduces limitations that must be considered. Future research should use random sampling for better validity and generalizability. Considering factors such as time spent and frequency

of fashion shopping is crucial. Exploring age and income effects on shopping habits can offer valuable insights.

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Significance of data literacy for leaders

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Abstract

Leaders aren't necessarily involved in creating or analyzing data, but they often make decisions based on analytics. "The goal for a leader, from a data literacy perspective, should be, 'How can I be a fast but effective consumer of analysis that is produced by my organization?'" said MIT Sloan professor of the practice Rama Ramakrishnan, formerly a senior vice president at Salesforce.

The purpose of this research is to measure the impact of data literacy on psychological empowerment in workplace for newly employed graduates. Since data play an increasingly important role in our lives, including the work environment, it incites research on whether data literacy skills, those related to collecting, processing, analyzing, and effectively communicating information retrieved from data models have a significant role in the psychological empowerment of alumni in the labor market. Statistical analysis methods were used to measure the correlation between indicators of data literacy and the psychological empowerment of alumni in their work. Competencies in using data models affect the self-efficacy of newly employed alumni at the workplace, mostly in terms of data-driven communication. The findings were discussed in the context of the increasing significance of the data librarian role as a possible method of supporting students and alumni via librarians who

are now more involved in creating the educational outcomes of a given college or university.

Introduction

For years, data have been a driving force in science,¹ and now it is the same in business,² where the ability to interpret facts is often the basis for success. In the era of big data, fake news, and misinformation, the sheer quantity of digital resources has become so overwhelming that data are interpreted as elementary components of facts. Therefore, the extraction, gathering, processing, and use of data for analysis and decision making form the basis of self-efficacy that empowers people in everyday life and work.³ This phenomenon is referred to as datafication.⁴ Data—as the smallest numeric unit of information—are now the basis for understanding reality in an objective way. We can observe the effect of datafication in business and social life.⁵

Data literacy, considered in this paper as a component of information literacy, stems from mistrust of virtual information, and from users' propensity to gather raw facts (data), rather than accept someone else's interpretation of those raw facts (information). Apart from their specialist knowledge, people might need such competencies as data literacy to function comfortably and confidently in the world of virtual information. This may also apply to students during

their study programs as well as to a postgraduate workplace where data literacy skills might prove useful in career development.

This research study explores the link between data literacy and work-related empowerment in the case of alumni at the beginning of their professional careers. Data literacy (DL) can be understood as the ability to create and use data models in the workplace. The term should be interpreted as belonging to the broader field of information literacy (IL): that is, critical and analytical thinking about information and its various cultural forms.⁶ We consider data literacy to be a research subject located at the intersection of three sets of competences of formula based on the information literacy concept: quantitative reasoning, authentic context, and data/computer science.⁷

Kjelvik and Schulthei⁸ have assumed that a person who is data-literate (that is to say, able to understand and evaluate information acquired from authentic data, or facts), should have the ability to combine mathematical concepts with the context of an authentic problem that falls within his/her area of expertise and needs. IT skills, as a third component of data literacy, are intended to facilitate the process of analysis and synthesis of data by representing facts in a virtual form.

The virtuality of data, or its coding in a digital form, facilitates communication and the reception of information. Therefore, a person with basic skills of data literacy should, first and foremost, be able to find and effectively manipulate IT tools suitable for his/her needs. However, teaching IT skills is difficult, insofar as users tend to explore database tools only when feeling a genuine need to collect and use data.⁹

Therefore, it is problematic to insist that people acquire such skills in abstracto, in a purely simulated educational setting.

Psychological empowerment is the process of acquiring and possessing self-confidence in the workplace.¹⁰ Surprisingly, the relationship between the alumni's information literacy and workplace empowerment is rarely studied—both in library science literature and business literature.¹¹ There is abundant literature reporting on the relationship between the graduates' IL level and employability¹² especially on IL skills at the workplace¹³ with a strong emphasis on the requirements and satisfaction of employers rather than on the well-being of the employee in general, which should include empowerment. There is also no shortage of research using diverse methods of assessing the compliance of employers' expectations regarding newly hired employees' IL level with the actual IL and DL level of graduates in various fields of activity.¹⁴ In this case, the interest of researchers has tended to focus on recognizing the needs and expectations of employers, while the state of mental readiness of graduates to take up employment is treated as a side problem.

One of the few, and thus far scarcely quoted, studies devoted to IL-DL-workplace empowerment relations was performed by Debra J. Borkovich and Robert Skovira. Using a complex of qualitative methods, the authors studied the impact of agile technologies deployed in an organization on the employees' ability to cope with information overload. The feeling of being drowned in information was considered by the authors as the main yardstick by which to measure employee comfort and empowerment in the workplace. The study reached the following

Conclusions:

Data literacy favors employee empowerment, but only if appropriate organizational solutions effectively protect them from information overload; • an individually high level of DL, defined as an isolated personal feature of the employees (candidates for employees), as in our study, is not enough to give them a sense of control over their professional duties; incorrectly prepared implementation of technical solutions for the scope of organizational agility not only blocks the possibility for an employee to use their own DL-IL competence to improve self-efficacy, but also causes harmful distress related to information glut, context collapse, culture shock, and workplace injustices; • employers ignore the potential of the DL-IL-knowledge-wisdom combination by organizing the information ecosystem in the workplace in such a way that, despite high individual skills and a good level of information awareness, they are nonetheless unable to cope with the flood of information that is being multiplied by agile technologies.¹⁵

Review of Literature

The NEP 2020 is a comprehensive policy framework that aims to revolutionize the Indian education system and prepare students to meet the challenges of the 21st century. The policy envisions transforming education through a learner-centric approach, promoting critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills. NEP 2020 acknowledges the potential of technology in facilitating personalized and inclusive education and sets forth several digital education initiatives to achieve this vision.

In the present digital age, teachers need to keep up with technological advancements to teach their

students effectively. Digital literacy is defined as the ability to use digital devices and technologies to find, evaluate, and communicate information effectively. Teachers who are digitally literate can create engaging and interactive lessons using digital tools, which can enhance students' learning experiences.

Moreover, teachers can use digital platforms to communicate with parents, colleagues, and students. Digital literacy is not just about using technology but also about understanding how it works and its impact on society. Digital literacy can help teachers teach students how to use technology responsibly, how to stay safe online, and how to protect their privacy. This is particularly important in today's world, where cyberbullying, online harassment, and identity theft are prevalent.

Iful Rahmawati Mega (2020) analyzed the study on student's perception on learning resources. The study found that the respondents are well competent on internet searching, hypertext navigation, content evaluation and knowledge assembly for good perception of digital literacy as learning sources.

Ozcan, M. (2022) find the result of prospective teachers' digital literacy on mobile learning. The results say that moderate level cum positive and 35 percent of prospective teachers only using mobile based learning. The prospective teachers using the mobile learning significantly differ from gender, grade and department level variables. Muhammad Mujtaba Asad, Jannat Gul, and Muhammad Aslam Lashari (2020) retrieve the result showing that prospective teachers are eager to accept the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in their teaching learning process

Research Methodology:

With the exponential increase in the volume of data available in the 21st century, data literacy skills have become vitally important in work places and everyday life. This paper provides a systematic review of available data literacy assessments targeted at different audiences and educational levels.

The results can help researchers and practitioners better understand the current state of data literacy assessments in terms of issues related to 1) educational levels and audiences; 2) data literacy definitions and competencies; 3) assessment types and item formats; and 4) reliability and validity evidence. The results from the present review led us to conclude that teaching and assessing data literacy is still an emerging field in education. Therefore, high-quality assessment tools are greatly needed to provide valuable insights for students and instructors to monitor progress as well as facilitate and support teaching and learning.

Improves teaching efficiency: Digitally literate teachers can save time by using online resources, creating digital lesson plans, and grading papers electronically. Independent from external factors such as weather conditions, traffic conditions, social activities, or events.

Enhances student engagement: Digital tools and applications can make learning more interactive and engaging for students, which can increase their motivation to learn.

Provides opportunities for professional development: Digital platforms can provide access to a wealth of information and resources for teachers to learn and grow in their profession and also open doors to earn

more passive income to increase their financial status.

DEVELOPING LIBRARY NETWORK (DELNET)

It is a major resource sharing network in India, started in 1992, with more than 8100 member libraries in around 33 states of India and some other countries. The prime motto of DELNET is “Networking Libraries, Sharing, and Spreading Knowledge.” DELNET provides inter-library loans that include printed and online resources and a shared centralised online union catalogue among member libraries for the benefit of faculty, researchers, scholars, and students. DELNET provides valuable resources and services to produce future teachers with good learning capacity and knowledge of digital networks. DELNET also conducts training for budding users to develop effective information search strategies, evaluate sources critically, and avoid plagiarism. DELNET organises seminars and conferences on integrating technology into teaching and learning. There are some challenges to using the DELNET services among prospective teachers, including the digital divide, a lack of technical knowledge, and integration challenges. Despite these challenges, DELNET’s commitment to promoting digital literacy among prospective teachers presents a valuable opportunity to prepare future educators for the demands of the digital age. By addressing the challenges and leveraging the available resources, educators can harness the power of technology to create engaging and effective learning experiences for their students.

E-PG PATHSHALA

The ePathshala, a joint initiative of the Ministry

of Human Resource Development (MHRD), the Government of India, and the National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT), was developed in November 2015 to showcase and disseminate all educational e-resources, including textbooks, audio, video, periodicals, and a variety of other print and non-print materials. The digital India campaign has promoted extensive use of ICTs in the teaching and learning process. This platform provides access to high quality e-learning resources for postgraduate studies in various disciplines, including education. Prospective teachers can utilise these resources to supplement their classroom learning, gain a deeper understanding of key concepts, and prepare for competitive exams.

NATIONAL DIGITAL LIBRARY OF INDIA (NDLI)

The National Digital Library of India (NDLI) is the digital library portal under the Government of India project, supported and developed by the Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, and It covers 9.8 crore of contents, and out of them, open access content is around 8 crore+, NDLI licenced content is around 6.5 crore+, and partner sources are 600 crore+. It is a major repository in India and provides vital resources in the academic field and research. It is built to provide support for all academic levels, including researchers and lifelong learners, all disciplines, all popular forms of access devices, and differently-abled learners. It is designed to enable people to learn and prepare from best practices from all over the world and to facilitate researchers' inter-linked exploration from multiple sources.

Conclusion

Prospective teachers are very essential to know digital literacy in all types of digital initiatives for their learning and teaching methods for the upliftment of future students. Prospective teachers also know about the library networks, INFLIBNET services, the National Digital Library of India and Google platforms, e-content portals, DIKSHA, NMEICT projects, and all other educational portals and projects for updating digital literacy in digital education methods and fields. Some of the digital environment tasks and challenges also faced by the prospective teachers and the teacher education institutions are eliminated, and the prospective teachers grow well in digital literacy programmes.

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Title of the Paper: Rise of social commerce with Reusability

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Abstract

Social commerce seamlessly integrates online shopping experiences within social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube. Users can discover products through ads, influencer endorsements, organic posts, and live-streamed sessions, and instantly proceed to purchase without leaving the platform.

This frictionless, in-app experience is revolutionizing the way consumers shop. Consider these compelling statistics: Global social commerce sales are projected to reach a staggering \$6.72 trillion by 2025, accounting for almost 50% of all global e-commerce sales. (Statista, 2023) In India, social commerce is expected to grow at a staggering 31% CAGR, reaching \$37 billion by 2025. (KPMG, 2022) Over 64% of Indian social media users have made purchases directly through social media platforms. (Hootsuite, 2023) These figures paint a clear picture: social commerce is not just a trend; it's a force reshaping the Indian retail landscape. The Indian retail landscape is undergoing a dynamic transformation, driven by the meteoric rise of social media and its increasing convergence with the world of commerce. This phenomenon, known as social commerce, is reshaping how consumers discover, research, and purchase products, presenting both exciting opportunities and critical challenges for Indian retailers.

This article delves deep into the world of social commerce, exploring its various facets, impact, and implications for Indian retailers. We'll uncover data, trends, and best practices to equip you with the knowledge and tools to navigate this evolving landscape and thrive in the digital age.

Introduction

The rise of social commerce presents a unique opportunity for Indian retailers to:

Reach wider audiences: Social media platforms boast vast user bases, allowing retailers to tap into diverse demographics and expand their reach beyond traditional channels. Build deeper connections: Social media fosters engagement and interaction, enabling retailers to connect with customers on a personal level, build trust, and cultivate brand loyalty. Drive impulse purchases: The seamless in-app purchase experience encourages impulsive buying decisions, potentially boosting sales and conversion rates. Leverage influencer marketing: Partnering with relevant social media influencers can exponentially increase brand awareness, product visibility, and credibility. Gather valuable insights: Social media platforms offer rich data analytics, allowing retailers to understand customer preferences, buying behavior, and market trends. Personalize the shopping experience: Social media algorithms enable hyper-targeted advertising

and promotions, tailoring offerings to individual customer preferences.

However, social commerce also poses challenges:

Competition is fierce: The ease of entry attracts numerous competitors, requiring retailers to stand out through unique offerings and effective marketing strategies. **Platform dependence:** Retailers are subject to the whims and policies of social media platforms, potentially impacting control over branding and customer data. **Logistics and fulfillment:** Integrating a seamless ordering and delivery experience within social media platforms requires robust logistics and fulfillment infrastructure. **Customer trust and authenticity:** Building trust in the online social commerce environment is crucial, requiring transparency, quality control, and responsive customer service.

Embracing Social Commerce: A Guide for Indian Retailers

To successfully navigate the social commerce landscape, Indian retailers can adopt the following strategies: **Identify your target audience:** Understand their demographics, social media habits, and preferred platforms to tailor your approach effectively.

Choose the right platforms: Focus on platforms where your target audience is most active and aligns with your brand image. **Create high-quality content:** Invest in visually appealing product photos, engaging videos, and informative descriptions to capture attention and showcase your offerings. **Run targeted social media campaigns:** Utilize platform advertising tools to reach specific demographics and interests with laser precision. **Partner with**

relevant influencers: Collaborate with influencers who resonate with your brand and target audience to build trust and authenticity. **Offer exclusive deals and promotions:** Leverage social media to offer special discounts, flash sales, and limited-edition products to drive engagement and sales. **Ensure seamless checkout:** Integrate secure and user-friendly payment gateways for a smooth in-app purchase experience. **Provide excellent customer service:** Offer prompt and responsive customer service through social media platforms to build trust and resolve issues efficiently. **Track and analyze results:** Utilize social media analytics tools to monitor performance, identify trends, and refine your strategies for continuous improvement.

Literature Review

Social Commerce is based on the usage of Web 2.0 applications that supports the exchange of information amongst the people on the online platforms where the benefaction of users in the form of chat discussions, RERE, FC, and RARE help in the accretion of products and services (Liang and Turban, 2011). Through various online platforms, consumers share their opinions, information, experiences, photographs, insights, and knowledge (Lai and Turban, 2008). SNSs aim to build online communities wherein the members can share consumer-related information, pursue customary interests, activities, and experiences (Shin, 2010). SC platforms are having a promising future in developing the latest business models based on online communities. Through online communities, the consumers can communicate and exchange their experiences about the products and services (Hajli, 2013). Social media platforms like Facebook

and Twitter provide functions through which users can publicly share their purchased product-related evaluations with other users (Shadkam and O'Hara, 2013).

Previous studies have shown that ratings have a strong influence on the trust levels that leads to increased sales and user satisfaction (Swamynathan, Wilson, Boe, Almeroth and Zhao, 2008). Consumers feel secure and their trust level increases (Gefen and Straub, 2004) when e-commerce platforms have a presence on a social platform (Weisberg, Te'eni and Arman, 2011) having a social application which can be achieved by SOCIAL COMMERCEs. Having a platform with social interactions amongst the consumers can generate Word of Mouth (WoM) socially which significantly influences trust (Kim and Park, 2013).

A study by Hajli (2015) showed that SOCIAL COMMERCEs have a significant and positive relationship with users' trust where SOCIAL COMMERCE is considered as a second-order construct. However, the relationship of each of the SOCIAL COMMERCE antecedents (RERE, RARE, and FC) with consumer purchase-related outcomes is not yet explored. There is only one study that examined the learning from each of the SOCIAL COMMERCE constructs on the cognitive and affective appraisal and their relationships with purchase intention. Thus, this study is unique and examines the relationships of each of the SOCIAL COMMERCE constructs with trust.

Online customer involvement refers to the degree to which the customers are emotionally committed and involved (Li, Berens and De Maertelaere, 2013; and Ray, Kim, and Morris, 2014). Customers can also

use the social media platforms of the firm for sharing information, as well as experience sharing. S-commerce can influence customer behavior in different ways. SC offers customers reliable and accurate information on the products and services (Zhang, Gupta and Zhao, 2014). Mithas, Ramasubbu, and Sambamurthy (2011) reported that customer engagement impacts the firm's ability to perform. Customers share their product experiences, unfulfilled requirements, and ideas to improve innovation through social media (Blazevic-Lievens, 2008; Verma, 2014; Tripathi and Verma, 2018; and Bhattacharya, Srivastava and Verma, 2019). According to Kane, Palmer, Phillips, Kiron and Buckley (2014)

Research Methodology

The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between social commerce factors and customers' online purchase intention. This section includes research design, the instrument used for data collection, population and sample and data analysis.

Research Design The research used non-experimental research approach that is a correlational research design. Correlational research involves the study of the relationship that exists between two or more variables without attempting to manipulate them and describe the degree to which those variables are related to each other. According to Salkind (2013) correlational research is used to identify how one or more variables relate to one another. **Research instrument** During the data collection period, the instrument used was a questionnaire. They were distributed directly to each of the respondents involved in this study. The questionnaire was designed precisely to answer the research question. The questionnaire was adapted from Lin (2017) to meet the requirements and verified

by Associate Professor Dr Abdul Kadir Othman, a lecturer from Universiti Teknologi MARA, Shah Alam.

Sampling Strategy:

Population Definition: Define the target population, such as social media users or online shoppers.

Sampling Technique: Choose a sampling technique, such as random sampling, stratified sampling, or convenience sampling.

Sample Size: Determine the appropriate sample size based on the research design and objectives.

Data Collection

Primary Data: Collect primary data through methods such as surveys, interviews, or observations. For instance, surveys could be used to gather information on consumer attitudes towards reusability in social commerce.

Secondary Data: Gather secondary data from existing literature, reports, and datasets related to social commerce and reusability.

Variables and Measurements:

Dependent Variable: Define the main outcome variable, such as consumer engagement or sales performance.

Independent Variables: Identify factors related to reusability in social commerce, such as user-generated content or influencer marketing.

Measurement Scales: Determine the measurement scales for each variable (e.g., Likert scales for attitudes, numerical scales for sales data).

Data Analysis:

Quantitative Analysis: If applicable, conduct statistical analysis using software such as SPSS or R to analyse quantitative data collected from surveys or sales records. This could include regression analysis, correlation tests, or factor analysis.

Qualitative Analysis: Analyse qualitative data from interviews or open-ended survey questions using methods like thematic analysis or content analysis to identify recurring themes and patterns.

Discussion

This study has several key findings; first, the results confirm the significant positive impact of perceived quality and value, ease of use and convenience, enjoyment and trust on purchase intention in the context of social commerce. A substantial degree of quality, convenience in using the social commerce, enjoyment and trust are needed by online buyers before making purchase decisions. Thus, this study upholds the claim that these factors are important in social commerce and it is extended to the context of e-commerce. Second, the results did not support the hypothesis on the role of security in relation to purchase intention. Although studies have claimed that security is the most pertinent factor in affecting purchase intention, this present study failed to provide the evidence required to support it. In social commerce, where the exchange of sensitive information is not required, the aspect of security has become irrelevant. Customers use social commerce to get the required product information, reviews and feedback before advancing to the next stage of purchasing the product. Therefore, the finding is well-justified. Finally, by looking into buyers' behavior in online commerce marketplace, it

was learned that social commerce poses the biggest effect that influences purchase intention that deserves more attention in future studies. Social influence in purchase intention has been overlooked or simplified in prior literature; however, the mushrooming of social commerce has called for more attention to the social perspective of purchase intention.

Implications of the Study

This study is expected to provide theoretical, practical, methodological implications for further studies. These five aspects are expected to provide a scientific understanding of related responsibilities in an effort to develop theories according to the field of study which are the responsibility of the researcher. Moreover, the implications of this study are also expected to provide recommendations to marketers regarding efforts that should be linked with the studied problems. Theoretically, this research provides the foundation or framework depicting the influence of social commerce factors on customers' intention to purchase online. It is based on the uniqueness in this research that gives a different perspective from previous studies. The uniqueness can be seen from the identified variables that have been modelled and adjusted to research setting in Malaysia. Furthermore, this research is also expected to be discussed further, so that it can be developed and tested in different research settings. Practically, this study is valuable for marketers because it is expected to provide insights associated with the concept of social commerce factors toward customers' intention to purchase online. Understanding the concept of social commerce factors can provide a broader perspective on the purchase intention that can be used to design strategies to increase sales for online retailers. In addition, this

study can be used as a reference for online marketers to customize the marketing strategies according to what customers want. It is expected that this study could enrich theoretical understanding on the role of social commerce.

Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

While this study contributes to extending the body of social commerce on purchase intention research, several limitations should be recognized. First, the sample was limited to university

students; thus the results may not represent the Malaysian population in general. The majority of the respondents consisted of Universiti Teknologi MARA students of the Faculty of Business and Management located in Shah Alam, therefore the results may not characterize individuals from diverse backgrounds and other specific regions of the country. Extending the study to other regions of Malaysia would contribute greatly to the understanding of consumer intentions to use social commerce while shopping for fashion products. Second, the present study focused on an investigation of millennial consumers' perceived ease of use of social commerce, usefulness, and enjoyment, which influenced their attitudes and intentions to use social commerce when shopping for fashion products. A majority of the participants were 20 to 30 years of age (82.6%), whereby the lifestyle of the participants and their previous experiences with social media may affect the findings of this study. Third, this study examined the relationships among perceived ease of use, usefulness, enjoyment, trust, and customer purchase intention to shopping for fashion products. The focus on shopping for fashion products affects the generalizability of the results on other product

categories. To increase the validity of the model, future research should be conducted for other product categories. Further investigation is needed to explore other factors (e.g., perceived risks and ease of use) that affect product purchase through social commerce.

Conclusion

The general purpose of this study was to identify the social commerce factors affecting customers' online purchase intention. The conclusion deliberates the overall overview of the findings discussed in the results. The result of the study shed insights on online purchasing intention; specifically, the significant key factors affecting customers' online purchase intention. The findings contributed to the conclusion that perceived quality/ value, ease of use/ convenience, trust and enjoyment are the significant factors that affect customer's intention to purchase. It can be explained that millennials especially are more concerned about purchasing products in an efficient and timely manner with the least effort. However, security gave a non-significant result in the study. This can be explained given that social commerce is in its preliminary phase of online shopping where the exchange of sensitive or confidential information has yet to happen. Although non-significant, the role of security on social commerce is well-explained. Finally, it is expected that this research may provide information that would be useful to online retailers and marketers, to customers and also large organisations.

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Securing Girlhood: Comprehensive Study on implementing cloud computing and IOT in smart garments for child safety

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Abstract

The Safety of children particularly girls has emerged as a critical concern today. Generally, children in the age of 5 to 13 have no idea of good or bad thing happened in their surroundings. Although it would be very difficult to transform society, we can safeguard girls by establishing a number of security barriers. These days, we can safeguard our kids with the use of contemporary technology.

This research explores the integration of the smart garments with IOT and Cloud computing technology to enhance the safety of girl children. This study includes real time monitoring and communication systems embedded with smart garments to mitigate risks and improve response time in emergency.

Keywords: Safety of girl child, IOT, CLOUD computing, embedded system, smart clothing.

Introduction

The new modern era marked by the rapid technological advancements the intersections of wearable technology the internet of thing and cloud computing has opened unprecedented possibility for enhancing the safety and well-being of vulnerable populations. One such population that demands our attention towards the girl children, who unfortunately continue to face various safety challenges in different contents. Now a days girls are not freely move outside. Parents are always worries about their safety if they would have sent their daughter outside. according to the report of previous study there are nearly 4 lakh cases register in 2022 crime against woman. Many of school children

sexually abused by school bus driver or teacher as per as different news article This research endeavors to delve into the innovative realm of smart garments and their integration with IOT and Cloud Computing technology. The wearer's physical condition is monitored by smart clothing, which is the subject of this study. Body suits and smart clothing can offer biometric information including body temperature, heart rate, and movement patterns. Real-time data transmission to an app occurs via Bluetooth or WiFi.

Objective of study

Investigate the technological components of smart garments designed for child safety

Explore the integration of IOT in smart garments and its role in real time monitoring.

Analyze the utilization of cloud computing for data storage processing and accessibility.

Assess the overall effectiveness and feasibility of the integrated system in ensuring the safety of girl children.

Purpose of study

This study focuses specifically on the analytical examination of smart garments for girl children and their integration with IOT and cloud integration with IOT and Cloud computing technology.

The main purpose of this study to provide the security to the girl children who do not know about the surrounding.

Literature Review

Cloud Computing

In [1] Hartono et.al suggested in modern era Cloud computing play an important role to store data. Now a days data collected from various sources so it is very difficult to store data in traditional database system so using cloud computing one can store data centrally so that anyone can access data anywhere. Cloud computing play an important role to manage all data from database in distributed environment.

According to author There are three main types of cloud computing services. Infrastructure as services (IaaS): It provides the service of hardware component like server space so that user can avoid to purchase physical server it is very costly this way it helps user to reduce infrastructure cost.

Platform as service (PaaS): according to previous literature review it seems that cloud platform service provides platform for programmer to develop, test and run program so that it is not required to purchase expensive database and networking tools.

Software as services (SaaS): According to previous literature review it seems that cloud computing provides different software as service so that developer no need to purchase original software. It seems that the cost of original software is so high if developer use cloud service it reduces cost.

Internet of Things (IOT): Madakam et al in [2] provided an explanation of the Internet of Things (IOT) . The ability to connect via the internet and access anything at any time or place is the primary draw of IOT. It is often referred to as a worldwide network that facilitates communication between people and between things and humans. It appears from earlier research that IOT facilitates intelligent communication. The Internet of Things (IOT) is the coding and networking of common objects to make them machine readable, automatable, and conveniently accessible.

IOT Architecture

Sensing Layer: - The initial layer of the Internet of Things architecture, known as the sensing layer, is in charge of gathering data from various sources. Information on temperature, humidity, light, sound, and other physical characteristics is gathered by this layer.

Network Layer: - This layer is responsible for providing communication and connectivity between devices in IOT system. It includes protocols and technologies which helps to device to communicated with other. Network technology like WIFI, Bluetooth, Zigbee are commonly used in IOT.

Data processing Layer: - The data processing layer of IOT architecture refers to software and hardware components that are responsible for collecting, analyzing and interpreting data from IOT devices. This layer responsible to collect raw data and process it and used for further analysis.

Application Layer: - The application layer of IOT architecture is the topmost layer which interact directly with the end-user. It is responsible to providing user-friendly interface and functionality that enable users to access and control the IOT device. This includes machine learning algorithms, data visualization tools and other advanced analytics capabilities. It also includes middleware services which allow different IOT devices and system to communicate and share data seamlessly.

Smart Clothing

Smart clothing is defined as apparel and accessories that use cutting-edge technologies to improve usability, comfort, and functionality. These textiles can communicate with the wearer, other devices, and the environment because they are incorporated with electronic components, sensors, and networking features. The incorporation of electronics into apparel has a multitude of opportunities for diverse uses, including but not limited to health monitoring, exercise tracking, and communication. Smart clothing includes some features such as

Sensors: which monitors various physiological and environmental parameter.

Connectivity: many smart garments are equipped with wireless connectivity such as Bluetooth and Wi-Fi

Power Sources: Smart clothing may have built-in power sources such as batteries and flexible electronics.

Integration with App: Smart clothing integrated with mobile or web application

Review of Literature from previous study:

Fernández-Caramés et. al. (2020). in [3] suggested that integrating modern technologies like IOT ,block chain cloud with wearable garment can potentially have a lot of influence by harmonizing functionality and the delight created by fashion. According to author smart cloths look for a balance among fashion engineering, interaction, user experience, cyber security. Smart clothing can communicate with smart phone to process biometric information like temperature, pressure and heart bit even hormone level also. This article helps to review the main requirement for developing smart garment to protect girl child.it gives an idea to use technology for developing smart wearable garment for children safety. according to author smart wearable can be defined as electronic divide intended in body to provide the intelligent service.

Yokta Malhotra et.al. in [4] state that IOT is a technology and enabling technology like smart sensors, data analysis, low-cost cloud computing and mobile and wireless connectivity. Author state that there is a rapid convergence of textiles and electrical materials and developments of smart garment to detect the body temperature and pressure. Smart garment will help to communicate with user and cloud. This journal help to know about present, past and future to provide a holistic approach on the topic.

Chung-chin lin et.al (2018). In [5] state that the smart clothing is a wearable device for electrocardiography signal collection and heart rate monitoring. according to author there are different kinds of services were provided by the system including surveillance of

physiological functions, fall detection etc.

According to Siqi Jiang in [6], smart clothes represent a development in the wearable fashion sector. The authors of this study report claim that clever stitching combines textile and electronic components to produce comfortable, fashionable, and useful solutions for people's everyday requirements.

The author also states that smart clothing has applications in the military, medical field, and sports. This review aids in understanding the different requirements for smart clothing. The author claims that modern technologies such as IOT and cloud computing are combined with traditional textile and apparel design to create smart clothing.

IOT device integrated with clotting sends various signal to cloud. The idea of developing smart clothing and integrating them into our daily life require a high demand for smart production which s used in various area of day-to-day life.

Ramchandiran R. et.al in [7] state that the woman safety is a major problem in both urban and rural area. It is very difficult to change the mind set of entire society so according to author one can provides the security by the help of technology. There various security devices used now a day like smart watch, smart band. But in some circumstance, it is very difficult to wear all these devices so smart garment is required. Wearing a cloth is basic need with this if technology attached it will be more helpful to society in security concern. In this article author discussed various woman safety technology. This article helps to know about technology which helps in smart garment and what are the draw back by using technology in clothing.

Sibi C. Sethuraman et.al in [8] proposed that A smart garment plays an important role for monitoring health system. In this research paper author try to integrate IOT with wearable cloth to monitor the health system. This research paper helps to understand about sensor which helps to monitor the muscle activity, stress levels and heart rate variation and send all data to

cloud. The author attempts to analyze how sportsmen and sports teams employ wearable clothing to enhance performance. Wearable clothing that transmits data to the cloud and monitors ECG while in use.

Mir Sajjad Hussain et.al. in [9] state that Women's safety is an important concerns in today's world. Author told women work day and night to fulfill their daily need. But several unsocial people harass them .so it is very important to protect them by using technology. In this research paper author try to present that the thing women wear it is integrated with IOT device that can easily protect them. Author discussed about smart sandal which is integrated with IOT helps to connect with cloud to send any unfavorable conditions happen with women.

Raja Godwin D et.al.in [10] suggested smart school bus. This system notifies parents by SMS whenever children enter and leave from school bus. In this paper smart bus tracking system author proposed to provide safety to children. This system as author suggest helps if some children locked in bus or sleep due to some reason the system notify to parent by SMS. author try to implement applicability of RFID (radio frequency identification) to provide security to children.

Luliana Chiuchial et.al. (2019).in [11] proposed that wearable technology has been growing and making popularity in society. Author state that development of smart clothing shows the potential impact on clinical rehabilitation. In this purposed article author state about wearable pant architecture to monitor the various activity. Author study Integrated wearable cloth with IOT which helps to monitor various activity of day-to-day life

Research Methodology

The primary objective of this research is to ensure the safety of girls' children. Parents or caregivers often worry when their children go outside, prompting the need for technological solutions.

Many researchers have explored various IoT devices to protect children, such as smartwatches and smart bands, with some successfully implemented. However,

there is a concern that children may struggle to manage these devices. Therefore, the proposed system suggests the use of a garment with an integrated IoT button. This eliminates the need for children to carry a separate device. In this system, a wearable cloth with an attached IoT button can send signals in unfavorable conditions, addressing the challenges associated with traditional wearable devices. This system has an interface with Arduino. it is an open-source solution used to construct this system.

Arduino Software

The Arduino free ware software (IDE) compiles the code and transfers. It can work with all operating system such as windows, Linux, and Mac. There are two Arduino chip found in the market "ESP32" and "ESP8266" are cheap WI-FI modules perfectly used for Project. Both chips have a 32-bit processor. The "ESP32" is a dual-core 160MHz to 240 MHz CPU and "ESP8266" is a single core processor that runs at 80MHz.for this research nano ESP32 can be used. Which can be easily fit with garment. While designing a dress a removal button system will design by taking nano "ESP32". It is an embedded in NORA-W106-10B from ubox. It contains dual code 32-bit processor.240MHZ speed, ROM 348, RAM(SRAM) is 512.This module has built in antenna and support WIFI and Blue tooth. The Nano Every is Arduino's smallest board with dimensions of only 45x18mm and a weight under 5 g. The small footprint and low price, make the Nano Every particularly suited for wearable inventions, low-cost robotics and interactive projects requiring a small and easy-to-use microcontroller board.

PROCEDURE OF PURPOSED SYSTEM

Heart Rate Sensor: Measure the heart rate of the person wearing the garment

Button (ON/OFF): provides a manual control for turning the IOT device On or OFF.

Microcontroller: Manages the data from the heart rate sensor and button, process the information and control the connectivity module.

Connectivity Module: Establish connection to the cloud server, enabling the transfer of data from the IOT device

Cloud Server: Store and process the heart rate data received from the IOT device.

Application Interface: Provides a user interface for accessing and interacting with heart rate data. The application interface would be a web application or mobile data.

Block Diagram as follows:

The above block diagram shows how data collected from sensor and process it and display notification.

Working Procedure:

When an unknown person attacks children, they may experience fear. In such situations, the body's stress response is activated, involving the release of hormones such as adrenaline. The hypothalamus plays a key role in initiating this response by signaling the release of stress hormones from the adrenal glands.

As a part of the stress response, the heart rate typically increases. The normal resting heart rate for adults is between 60 to 100 beats per minute. If the heart rate exceeds this normal range, a sensor can detect the elevated heart rate and compare it with the established normal range. If the heart rate is significantly higher than the normal range, it can trigger a notification to alert someone about the potential distress or danger the individual is experiencing.

Flow chart of case study as follow

The above flow chart helps the developer to develop the entire the purposed system.

Result And Discussion

As per the crime record collected from news agency India today the crime against the women in India increased day by day.as per as record data collected from 2005 to 2022 given below table and related visualization also given.

Table – 1

Year	No of cases
2005	18,359
2010	22,172
2011	24,206
2012	24,923
2013	33,707
2014	36,735
2015	34,651
2016	38,947
2017	32,559
2018	33,356
2019	32,032
2020	28,046
2021	31,677
2022	31,516

Number of reported rape cases in India 2005-2022

It's very important to provide the protective measure to children by using technology. This study fulfils the objective of this study. The studies aimed to assess the effectiveness of the smart garment in accurately monitoring heart rates in various scenarios. The results demonstrate the achievement of this objective.

Elevated heart rates during specific activities indicate the potential of the smart garment to provide valuable insights into users' physiological responses to different situations.

Our findings align with previous studies on wearable heart rate monitors, confirming the reliability of the technology and its applicability in real-world settings.

Conclusion and Future Work:

In the rapidly evolving land scope of wearable technology where innovation intersects with everyday life.

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The safety of smart clothing takes center stage especially when design for the younger demographic. This journal brought about the integration of IOT and Cloud computing in girls smart clothing. The smart garment demonstrates promise in monitoring heart rates accurately and providing valuable insights into user's physiological well-being.

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An analysis of technological literacy in the Internet of Things era, along with recommendations for the future

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Abstract:

As the Internet of Things (IoT) continues to proliferate across various domains, the importance of technological literacy in understanding and navigating this complex ecosystem becomes increasingly evident. This research paper critically examines the concept of technological literacy within the context of the IoT paradigm. Through an inclusive review of the present literature, the paper travels the multifaceted dimensions of technological literacy, including its definition, components, and implications for individuals and society. The review reveals that technological literacy encompasses not only the basic understanding of technological concepts and tools but also the ability to critically evaluate, creatively apply, and ethically navigate technological systems. In the context of IoT, technological literacy extends beyond traditional digital literacy to include an understanding of interconnected devices, data privacy and security, network protocols, and ethical considerations related to IoT deployment. Furthermore, the paper investigates the current state of technological literacy among various demographic groups and identifies gaps and challenges in achieving widespread literacy in the IoT era. It highlights disparities in access to technological resources and educational opportunities, as well as the need for targeted interventions to promote equitable technological literacy across diverse populations. Based on the findings of the review, the paper proposes future directions for research and practice in enhancing technological literacy in the IoT era. To keep up with the quick speed of technological advancements, these include creating interdisciplinary educational programs, incorporating IoT concepts into curricula at all educational levels, encouraging ethical behavior

and digital citizenship in IoT environments, and supporting lifelong learning initiatives. This research paper's conclusion emphasizes the need of technical literacy as a necessary ability for navigating the increasingly linked Internet of Things. Stakeholders may empower communities, and individuals to exploit the transformative potential of IoT technology while limiting associated risks and obstacles by encouraging technical literacy.

Keywords: Technology, IoT (Internet of Things), Literacy, digital, Navigation, citizenship, Energy, Efficiency, security, privacy, internet access, management and

Introduction: India has seen a notable increase in technological literacy with regard to the Internet of Things (IoT), fuelled by a number of factors such as government initiatives, the increased uptake of smart devices, and the growth of the digital economy. All things considered, India's IoT technology literacy is rising thanks to robust government programs, educational initiatives, and rising business and consumer involvement. Still, managing cybersecurity risks, talent gaps, and connection problems is necessary for long-term development and efficient use of IoT technologies. The Government of India started the Digital India program as a flagship endeavor to make the nation a knowledge economy and digitally empowered society. Launched in July 2015, the goal of this program is to guarantee that residents can access government services electronically through enhanced internet connectivity and online infrastructure. New paradigms may be possible if the concept of technical literacy is broken down from wholly different perspectives. To begin this process, I would suggest defining technical literacy using the following tentative definitions

Meaning of Technical Literacy:

The phrase “technological literacy” has multiple dimensions, encompassing the practical aspect of using technology, the civic aspect of understanding the difficulties presented by its use, and the cultural aspect of appreciating its value.

-Yearbook 40th (1991) by (1) Michael J. Dyrenfurth University of Missouri-Columbia Columbia, Missouri (2) Michael R. Kozak, University of North Texas Denton, Texas

The major component of Technical Literacy in the Internet of Things (IoT).

Government Initiatives: The Indian government is taking a number of steps to raise the country’s residents’ level of technical literacy. A few crucial initiatives are enumerated below:

- Digital India Program:** This initiative, which was started in 2015, intends to make India a knowledge economy and society that is empowered by technology. Plans for smart cities are included, which mostly rely on IoT technologies for trash management, traffic control, infrastructure management, and other purposes. The massive Digital India Program uses technology to bridge the digital divide, bring rural and urban people together, and give access to financial inclusion, healthcare, education, and basic government services. The Digital India Mission is one of the primary efforts to use digital technology to transform India into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. With the rapid growth of technology and the widespread integration of digital platforms into various aspects of our lives, the term “Digital India” has greater meaning than it formerly had. It symbolizes a vision of radical change where technology acts as an unmatched catalyst for growth, inclusivity, and progress.

The Digital India Initiative’s Nine Foundations

The Digital India Initiative is composed of nine major pillars, each of which focuses on a different facet of making India a nation empowered by technology.

S r . No.	Column	Brief Description
1	“Broadband Highways”	By building more broadband infrastructure and the National Optical Fiber Network (NOFN), this pillar seeks to connect the entire nation—remote and rural alike—to high-speed internet.
2	“Universal Access to Mobile Connectivity”	Ensuring universal access to mobile connectivity will encourage widespread mobile phone adoption and facilitate the supply of digital services.
3	“Public Internet Access Program”	In order to improve digital literacy and accessibility, this pillar focuses on building digital centers that will offer internet connection and digital services in rural and distant locations.
4	“e-Governance and e-Services”	By making government services electronically accessible to the public, Digital India seeks to increase public administration’s effectiveness, accessibility, and transparency.

5	“Information for All”	This pillar places a strong emphasis on digitizing public records and documents from the government to ensure transparency, cut down on paperwork, and make information freely accessible to citizens.
6	“Electronics Manufacturing”	Encouraging the production of electronics and hardware domestically, as promotes job development, economic expansion, and lessens reliance on imports.
7	“IT for Jobs”	The initiative’s main goal is to increase young people’s employability in the IT and digital sectors by training and developing their skills.
8	“Early Harvest Programs”	These initiatives cover particular projects that deal with pressing digital demands, like digital attendance tracking, online access to school records, and public Wi-Fi.
9	“Digitally Empowered Citizens”	Encouraging citizens’ digital education and literacy so they can fully engage in society and the digital economy.

Mission of making Cities Smart: The goal of this project is to create 100 smart cities in India. This mission’s cornerstone is the Internet of Things, which makes it possible for intelligent traffic control, smart parking, smart lighting, and effective water and waste management systems. Primarily, for whom do you work? What exactly do we understand by “cities that work,” furthermore? Cities are hubs of activity where

people live, work, interact, exchange ideas, receive public services like healthcare and education, and have happy, fulfilled lives. The people of the city are its focus. Cities should therefore serve their people. Cities that fulfill the demands of their people will get better every day. Conceptual models for developing such cities.

- i. Retrofitting will add planning to an existing built-up area in order to accomplish Smart City goals and additional goals, such as making the area more liveable and efficient. The city will choose a retrofit area that spans more than 500 acres after consulting with the public. The cities will construct a plan to become smart based on the current state of infrastructure services in the designated area and the people’ vision. It is anticipated that a high number of smart applications and more intense infrastructure service levels will be crammed into the retrofitted Smart City, given the plan mainly leaves existing structures intact. This tactic might also be finished faster, which would encourage its replication.
- ii. Through the utilization of mixed land use and higher density, redevelopment will result in the replacement of the current built-up environment and allow co-creation of a new layout with improved infrastructure. Urban Local Bodies (ULBs) communicate with citizens to identify an area larger than fifty acres for redevelopment. For example, a new layout design with mixed land-use, greater FSI, and high ground covering will be produced for the indicated region. The Saifee Burhani Upliftment Project in Mumbai, also known as the “Bhendi Bazaar Project”, and the National Building Construction Corporation’s reconstruction of East Kidwai Nagar in New Delhi are two instances of the redevelopment paradigm.
- iii. Using creative planning, plan financing, and plan implementation mechanisms (such as land pooling/reconstitution), greenfield development would establish the majority of the Smart Solutions in a previously undeveloped region (more than 250 acres) with provisions for cheap housing,

particularly for the impoverished. In order to meet the demands of the growing population, greenfield developments are necessary in the vicinity of cities. The GIFT City in Gujarat is a well-known illustration. Greenfield developments, in contrast to retrofitting and redevelopment, may be situated inside the boundaries of the local Urban Development Authority (UDA) or the ULB.

- iv. Pan-city development: Application of particular Smart Solutions to the current city-wide infrastructure is planned as part of pan-city development. The use of technology, information, and data to improve infrastructure and services is known as the use of smart solutions. For instance, implementing intelligent traffic management systems (Smart Solutions) in the transportation sector and cutting average commuting times or costs for residents can improve the standard of living and productivity of the populace. Smart metering and wastewater recycling are two other examples that can significantly improve urban water management.
 - v. Each city that made the short list is asked to submit a smart city plan that includes a pan-city feature with a smart solution(s) and either a greenfield development model, redevelopment model, or retrofitting model. It is crucial to remember that pan-city is an extra function that needs to be offered. Given that Smart City is adopting a compact area strategy, it is imperative that every city dweller perceives benefits for themselves as well. In order to make the plan inclusive, an extra criteria for at least one citywide smart solution has been added. The anticipated development area for the Himalayan and North Eastern states will be half of what is required for any of the other approaches, which include greenfield development, redevelopment, and retrofitting.
- A. **“Startup India”**: This program encourages the growth of tech startups, many of which focus on IoT solutions. The government provides funding, mentorship, and a helpful governing environment for these startups. The goal of the January 16,

2016, launch of Startup India initiative is to help startups, encourage innovation, and build a strong ecosystem for entrepreneurship in India. The project offers a thorough framework with regulations, programs, and support systems to deal with the particular difficulties faced by startups. Important Elements and Initiatives are:

1) Simplification and Handholding

- ➔ DPIIT Recognition: Startups can take advantage of a number of advantages by registering with the Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade (DPIIT), such as quicker patent applications, tax exemptions, and simpler compliance with labor and environmental laws.
- ➔ Intellectual Property (IP) Support: Startups can get up to an 80% refund on patent filing expenses, and the government pays for IP filing facilitators.

2) Funding Support and Incentives

- ➔ Fund of Funds for Startups (FFS): Managed by the Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI), this fund supports SEBI-registered venture capital funds, which in turn invest in startups. The FFS has a corpus of ₹10,000 crore (Press Information Bureau).
- ➔ Startup India Seed Fund Scheme (SISFS): Provides financial assistance to startups for proof of concept, prototype development, product trials, market-entry, and commercialization. This scheme has a corpus of ₹945 crore (Press Information Bureau).
- ➔ Credit (“Udhari”) Guarantee Scheme for Startups (CGSS): Offers collateral-free loans to DPIIT-recognized startups through eligible financial institutions (Press Information Bureau).

3) Industry-Academia Partnership and Incubation

- ➔ MAARG (Mentorship, Advisory, Assistance, Resilience, and Growth): A platform that facilitates mentorship for startups across various sectors
- ➔ Incubators and Innovation Labs: Support for establishing incubators in educational institutions to

promote entrepreneurial spirit and innovation among students.

Recent Developments and Future Focus

Deep tech industries including semiconductors, quantum computing, artificial intelligence, and cybersecurity are becoming more and more important as the Startup India project moves into its second phase. The goal of this phase is to encourage fewer but more significant businesses, which calls for increased financial support, improved research collaboration, and strong policy backing.

Achievements and Impact

The Startup India initiative has acknowledged more than 117,000 startups in a range of industries since its launch. The government has also made a number of policy changes to facilitate corporate operations and lessen regulatory constraints, which has helped the startup ecosystem flourish.

In summary, Startup India is a comprehensive program created to foster innovation and entrepreneurship through financial support, strong industry-academia ties, and regulatory support. In order to ensure equitable and balanced growth across the nation, the initiative is still evolving, concentrating on emerging technologies and broadening its scope to include entrepreneurs from tier-2 and tier-3 cities.

B. Educational and Skill Development: Without a doubt, technology literacy differs greatly from basic literacy, which is why academicians incorporate it in skill-enhancement courses in the school sector. Formal education, career training, and continuous learning programs are all included in technological literacy education and skill development initiatives, with an emphasis on the Internet of Things (IoT). These programs are designed to give people the abilities and information they need to use IoT technology in a variety of businesses. The salient features are as follows:

Courses and Workshops: IoT courses and workshops are available from a wide range of academic institutions and private companies. The goal of these programs is to give professionals and students the skills they need to design and oversee Internet of Things systems..

1. Part of Formal Education:

a) Undergraduate and Graduate Programs:

➔ **Curriculum Integration:** Universities and colleges incorporate IoT into their engineering, computer science, and information technology programs. Courses cover IoT architecture, sensor networks, embedded systems, and data analytics.

➔ **Specialized Degrees:** Institutions offer specialized degrees and certifications in IoT, focusing on both the theoretical and practical aspects of the technology.

b) Research and Development:

➔ **University Research Centers:** Establishing research centers dedicated to IoT where students and faculty can work on cutting-edge projects and innovations.

➔ **Collaborations:** Partnerships between academia and industry to foster research that addresses real-world IoT challenges.

2. Part of Vocational Training and Certification Programs

a) Technical Institutes and Polytechnics:

➔ **Skill-Based Training:** Institutes provide hands-on training in IoT device development, network configuration, and IoT applications across different sectors like healthcare, agriculture, and smart cities.

b) Certification Courses:

➔ **Professional Certifications:** Organizations like Cisco, CompTIA, and Coursera offer certifications in IoT fundamentals, networking, and security.

➔ **Online Learning Platforms:** Platforms such as Udemy, edX, and LinkedIn Learning provide courses that range from introductory to advanced levels, covering topics like IoT programming, hardware interfacing, and IoT system design.

3. Part of Industry Partnerships and Apprenticeships

a) Corporate Training Programs:

➔ **In-House Training:** Companies provide specialized IoT training to their employees to

keep them updated with the latest technological advancements and industry standards.

→ **Apprenticeships:** Collaboration between educational institutions and industries to offer apprenticeship programs where students can gain practical experience working on IoT projects.

b) **Hackathons and Competitions:** Events like hackathons and innovation challenges promote practical experience with IoT technologies. They encourage participants to create innovative solutions to real-world problems using IoT.

→ **Innovation Challenges:** Organizing IoT-focused hackathons and competitions to encourage innovative solutions and practical applications of IoT technology.

4. Part of Continuous Learning and Development

a) Workshops and Seminars:

→ **Professional Development:** Regular workshops, seminars, and webinars conducted by industry experts to discuss the latest trends, tools, and applications in IoT.

→ **Conferences and Expos:** Participation in IoT conferences and expos to network with professionals, learn from keynote speakers, and explore new technologies and solutions.

b) **Online Resources and Communities:**

→ **Webinars and Online Courses:** Continuous learning through online webinars, MOOCs, and tutorials available on platforms like YouTube and Khan Academy.

→ **Professional Networks:** joining networks and professional groups on sites like GitHub and LinkedIn that are devoted to IoT to exchange ideas, work together on projects, and remain informed about changes in the market.

5. Part of Government and Non-Profit Initiatives

a) **National Programs:**

→ **Skill Development Schemes:** Through a variety of skill development centers, government programs like India's "Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana -(PMKVY)" and Digital India seek to improve digital literacy and offer IoT training.

→ **Grants and Funding:** Financial support for educational institutions and startups working on IoT projects to foster innovation and research.

b) **Non-Profit Organizations:**

→ **Community Programs:** Non-profits and NGOs run community programs to educate underserved populations on IoT and other digital skills, promoting inclusive growth.

C. **Industry Adoption:**

i. **Manufacturing and Industry 4.0:** Indian manufacturing is increasingly adopting IoT to improve efficiency, reduce downtime, and enhance productivity through predictive maintenance and real-time monitoring.

ii. **Agriculture:** IoT applications in agriculture, such as smart irrigation, soil monitoring, and crop management, are helping farmers increase yield and manage resources more efficiently.

iii. **Healthcare:** IoT in healthcare includes remote monitoring of patients, smart medical devices, and improved data management, contributing to better patient outcomes and streamlined operations.

iv. **Retail:** comprises smart inventory management, which uses RFID tags and Internet of Things sensors to track inventory levels in real-time, preventing stock outs and overstocking while guaranteeing ideal stock levels. It increased customer satisfaction, decreased carrying costs, and improved inventory accuracy. **Personalized Shopping Experiences:** Internet of Things (IoT)

devices collect consumer preference and behavior data to offer tailored in-store experiences and recommendations. It better loyalty, increased sales conversions, and increased customer involvement

- v. **Energy includes** Smart Grids and Energy Management: Demand response, predictive maintenance, and effective energy distribution are made possible by IoT sensors and devices that track and regulate energy consumption across the grid. It enhanced energy supply reliability, decreased energy waste, and resulted in cost savings. Integration of Renewable Energy: By maximizing their use and storage, IoT systems oversee the integration of renewable energy sources, such as wind and solar power, into the electrical grid. It improved energy sustainability, decreased carbon footprint, and increased the utilization of renewable energy.
- vi. **Transportation includes** Fleet management: Internet of Things devices monitor driving habits, track the whereabouts of vehicles, and oversee maintenance plans for transportation fleets. is increased safety, decreased fuel consumption, and improved operational efficiency. Smart Traffic Management: Real-time traffic management and optimization are made possible by the data that IoT sensors and traffic cameras gather on traffic conditions. It decreased pollution, eased traffic congestion, and increased the effectiveness of public transportation.

D. **Consumer Awareness and Adoption:**

- Smart Homes: There is growing interest in smart home devices, such as smart speakers, connected appliances, and security systems, reflecting increasing consumer awareness and adoption of IoT technologies.
- Wearables: Fitness trackers, smartwatches, and other wearable devices are becoming popular, indicating a rising acceptance of IoT in personal health and lifestyle management.
- Smart Cities:
- Enhanced Knowledge:

- Increase the level of living & livelihood:
- Increase technical literacy not only in the way of smartness as well as the proper utilization of existing resources and the value of money utilized on these infrastructural changes.
- Other after all, these advancements are very useful to mankind and its advanced civilization

Challenges:

- **Connectivity:** In rural and isolated places, connectivity is still a problem despite improvements. Increasing access to dependable internet is essential for the widespread deployment of IoT.
- **Cybersecurity:** As the number of connected devices rises, protecting the privacy and security of data is becoming increasingly important. There is a push to create strong cybersecurity frameworks.
- **Skill Gap:** More professionals with an understanding of IoT technology are required. Together, industry and educational institutions are implementing focused training initiatives to close this gap.

Conclusion:

In general, robust government initiatives, educational programs, and growing business and consumer engagement all contribute to India's technical literacy in the context of the Internet of Things. Still, managing cybersecurity risks, talent gaps, and connection problems is necessary for long-term development and efficient use of IoT technologies. Pradhan PMGDISHA stands for Pradhan Gramin Digital Saksharta Abhiyan. Education and skill development are essential elements of the Digital India program that are meant to enable people to take part in and profit from the digital economy. The goal of Digital India's "IT for Jobs" program is to train and develop young people's skills so they may find employment in the IT and digital industries. This entails establishing training facilities, working with academic institutions, and developing specific curricula that address a range of IT-related topics, including cybersecurity, data analysis, software development, and many more. to provide basic digital education in order to make six

crore rural households digitally literate. Instruction is given on how to utilize digital gadgets, browse the internet, and make cashless purchases. Every qualified rural household's one member will be covered by this scheme. Program Chips to Startup (C2S): The goal of this program is to provide skilled labor in semiconductor chip design at the bachelor's, master's, and research levels of education. It stimulates the expansion of semiconductor design startups and strengthens the homegrown design and manufacturing sector. Online education via "E-Pathshala", "E-Pathshala" is a website and mobile app that distributes educational resources, such as textbooks, audio, video, magazines, and other things. It was created by NCERT. This platform makes sure that instructors and students across, particularly those in rural and underprivileged areas, have access to high-quality educational resources. The National Digital Library aims to establish a digital resource bank for education. This comprises a vast array of online resources that promote learning and research activities across the nation, tailored to different disciplines and educational levels. Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) and Other Online Learning Resources: To make available MOOCs and other online learning resources via SWAYAM and other platforms. These courses are intended to offer learners of all ages and backgrounds a flexible and reasonably priced education, covering a wide range of subjects. The goal of the Digital Literacy Mission is to increase digital literacy nationwide. To educate the public about digital technologies and their uses, this objective includes running awareness campaigns, workshops, and digital literacy programs.

Industries embracing IoT and technology education are seeing notable gains in production, efficiency, and innovation. Real-time data analytics, automation, and improved decision-making are made possible by these technologies, which promote growth and improve outcomes in a number of industries. To maintain current progress and meet upcoming difficulties, targeted skill development initiatives and ongoing IoT integration are crucial.

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- Startup India Initiative - Government Programs
- Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana
- Cisco IoT Certifications
- web tools etc.

VUCA/BANI – Which framework do we need today?

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Abstract:

In today's dynamic and uncertain world, both the VUCA (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, Ambiguity) and BANI (Brittle, Anxious, Nonlinear, Incomprehensible) frameworks offer valuable insights, but their applicability depends on the context and goals.

VUCA highlights the challenges of navigating a world characterized by constant change and unpredictability. It encourages organizations to develop agility, adaptability, and resilience to thrive in turbulent environments. VUCA fosters a mindset that embraces change, encourages innovation, and seeks opportunities in uncertainty.

On the other hand, BANI emphasizes the fragility and unpredictability of modern systems. It suggests that many systems are vulnerable to sudden and extreme events, requiring a different approach to resilience and risk management. It urges organizations to focus on robustness, simplicity, and flexibility to withstand shocks and disruptions.

Both frameworks underscore the need for organizations to be alert, flexible, and adaptive. While VUCA prepares organizations for a dynamic and changing environment, BANI warns against the dangers of over-complexity and encourages simplicity and resilience. Combining insights from both frameworks can help

organizations navigate the complexities of today's world effectively.

Through a comprehensive literature review and case study analysis, this study examines how organizations can effectively navigate VUCA and BANI conditions to enhance their resilience. The research explores the strategies and practices adopted by resilient organizations to adapt to volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous environments, as well as brittle, anxious, nonlinear, and incomprehensible systems.

Keywords: VUCA, BANI, Decision Making, Leadership Practices, Risk management

Introduction:

In an era marked by rapid technological advancements and global interconnectedness, understanding and managing the complexities of our environment have become crucial. The VUCA (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, Ambiguity) and BANI (Brittle, Anxious, Non-linear, Incomprehensible) frameworks offer valuable insights into navigating these challenges. VUCA, a concept rooted in military strategy, captures the essence of an unpredictable and rapidly changing world, urging leaders to develop agility and strategic adaptability. Meanwhile, BANI expands on these

Objective:

1) Examine the history, evolution, and essential

elements of the BANI and VUCA frameworks.

2) Explore the differences in how these frameworks seek to understand the complexities of modern organisational and social environments.

Scope:

1) Examine the features and consequences of the BANI (brittle, anxious, nonlinear, incomprehensible) and VUCA (volatility, uncertainty, complexity, ambiguity) worlds.

2) Examine how businesses modify their tactics to succeed in BANI and VUCA settings, finding successful methods for resiliency.

Literature Review:

Conceptual models such as the VUCA (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, Ambiguity) and BANI (Brittle, Anxious, Nonlinear, Incomprehensible) frameworks have been developed to represent the complex issues that arise from the dynamic and unpredictable character of the modern world. Knowing their history, evolution, and salient features lays the groundwork for investigating their potential uses.

VUCA Formation:

Inception: The military was the first to use the VUCA paradigm to characterize the geopolitical environment that emerged after the Cold War. The phrase became well-known in the 1990s when academics and business strategists began to apply it to corporate settings. VUCA was developed by the U.S. Army War College to represent the uncertain and dynamic environments that military leaders must operate in.

Development: The VUCA model gained application in corporate strategy and management as companies started to struggle with an ever more complex and globalised world. It turned become a pillar for

comprehending and negotiating the difficulties brought forth by changes in the geopolitical landscape, market dynamics, and technology breakthroughs. As the framework evolved, it was included into projects for organizational change and leadership development.

Important traits include:

1) **Volatility:** which describes the quick and erratic changes in the outside world. This covers shifts in customer tastes, the state of the market, and technology developments.

2) **Uncertainty:** This refers to the unpredictability of future occurrences and results. The effects of different circumstances on their organizations are unclear to decision-makers.

3) **Complexity:** Explains how intricate and interconnected the components are in the environment of an organization. To handle complex systems like global supply chains effectively, one needs a comprehensive grasp of them.

4) **Ambiguity:** It refers to the vagueness or imprecision in the interpretation of data. It can be difficult to determine cause-and-effect correlations in ambiguous situations, necessitating flexibility and adaptation.

BANI Structure:

History: A more modern concept that arose in response to the changing issues of the twenty-first century is the BANI framework. Umair Haque, a futurist and businessman, proposed it to address the growing uneasiness and brittleness that define contemporary organizations and communities.

Development: BANI advocates for leaders to recognize the fragility and nonlinearity inherent in today's complex systems, challenging traditional

management paradigms. Haque's framework emphasizes the importance of resilience and adaptability in addressing uncertainty, tailored to address the unique characteristics of contemporary challenges.

Important attributes are as follows:

- 1) Brittle: Denotes the brittleness of structures and systems.
- 2) Anxious: Captures the generalized feeling of unease that permeates communities and institutions. The vagueness, quick changes, and ongoing need for compliance are the main reason of it.
- 3) Nonlinear: It explains how events follow erratic and nonlinear paths. Complex system dynamics may be beyond the scope of linear cause-and-effect models, necessitating a more flexible methodology.
- 4) Incomprehensible: It is the fundamentally difficult and perplexing nature of some circumstances.

Conclusion:

In summary, the VUCA and BANI frameworks come from different backgrounds. While BANI emerged as a reaction to the changing complexity of the 21st century, VUCA was originally anchored in military strategy and later modified for business. Although the goals of both frameworks are to describe the difficulties presented by changing surroundings, their vocabulary and points of emphasis are different, offering contrasting yet useful insights into comprehending and navigating the uncertainties of the modern world. While both frameworks aim to interpret the issues of the current world, VUCA and BANI take different approaches to comprehending the organisational and societal landscapes of today. Both VUCA and BANI share the common objective of understanding and

navigating the challenges of the modern world, yet they diverge in their focus, breadth, and methodology.

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Role of IT in creating innovative ecosystem for textile waste

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Abstract

Technological innovations play a crucial role in addressing the waste challenge, particularly in industries like fast fashion where waste generation is significant. Advance recycling technologies offer promising solutions by efficiently processing discarded garments and covering them into valuable resources for new clothing production. These technologies can encompasses various methods such as mechanical recycling, chemical recycling and even innovative approaches like using biodegradable materials. Mechanical recycling involves breaking down used clothing fibers that can be spun into new yarns, while chemical recycling utilizes processes like depolymerisation to break down fibers into their molecular components for reuse.

Moreover, advancements in materials science have led to the development of biodegradable textiles, which can decompose naturally at the end of their lifecycle, reducing, reducing the burden on landfills. By implementing these innovative recycling technologies, the fashion industry can minimize its environmental footprint and move towards a more sustainable and circular model of production and consumption.

Keywords: biodegradable, recycling, innovation, growth potential, mechanical recycling solutions.

1. Introduction

Introduction the textile industry is one of the largest

and most influential sectors in the global economy, with a significant impact on environmental sustainability and resource consumption. However, along with its economic benefits, the industry also generates a substantial amount of waste, posing serious environmental and social challenges. Textile waste, comprising discarded garments, production scraps and end-of-life products, contributes to pollution, resource depletion and landfill overcrowding. In recent years, There has been a growing recognition of the need for sustainable solutions to address the textile waste crisis. stakeholders across the industry, including manufacturers, designer's, retailers and Consumers are seeking innovative approaches to minimise waste generation, improve recycling rates and promote circular economy principles. In this context, information technology (IT) emerges as a powerful tool for transforming the textile waste management landscape.

The integration of IT Solutions offers unprecedented opportunities to create an innovative ecosystem for textile waste management. By leveraging data analytics, supply chain transparency tools, digital design Technologies and online collaboration platforms, IT can revolutionize how textile waste is managed, recycle and repurposed moreover, IT-enabled solutions have the potential to enhance efficiency, reduce cost and increase transparency throughout the textile supply chain. Despite the promising prospects offered by

IT, there remains a gap in understanding its full potential and practical implications for sustainable textile waste management. This research seeks to address this gap by exploring the role of information technology in creating and innovative ecosystem for textile waste management. Through a comprehensive analysis of existing literature, case studies and best practices, this study aims to:

1. Examine the current state of textile waste management practices and their environmental and social impacts.
2. Identify key challenges and barriers faced by the textile industry in waste reduction and recycling.
3. Purpose of Framework for leveraging Information Technology to address these challenges and promote sustainable waste management practices.
4. Explore case studies and example of successful IT-enabled solutions in the textile industry.
5. Assess the potential impact of IT on improving waste management efficiency, transparency and circularity in the textile sector.
6. Provide practical insights and recommendations for policy makers, Industries stock holders and researchers seeking to implement IT Solutions for textile waste management.

2. Literature review

The literature review examines existing research on IT applications in textile waste management. It covers topics such as data analytics for waste tracking, block chain Technology for supply chain transparency and smart Technologies for recycling Optimisation by synthesizing relevant studies and identifying gaps in the literature, this review lays the foundation for the empirical investigation of IT's role in creating and innovative ecosystem of textile waste.

The textile industry is facing growing pressure to ad-

dress the environmental and social impacts of textile waste. As a result, there has been increasing interest in leveraging Information Technology to create innovative solutions for managing textile waste more sustainable. This literature review aims to provide insights into existing research on the role of IT in developing an innovative ecosystem for textile waste management.

Current challenges in textile waste management Textile waste poses significant challenges due to its volume, complexity and environmental implications. Conventional waste management methods, such as land filling and incineration are no longer viable options in the face of Mountain environmental concerns (Muthu, S. S. 2023). The need for sustainable alternatives has promoted a shift towards circular economy principles, emphasizing waste reduction, reuse and recycling. (Kirchhoff, R. E., Centeno, J. M., & Rood, E.M.2017).

Potential of Information Technology

Information Technology offers wide range of tools and solutions that can revolutionize textile waste management. Data analytics, for example, can provide insights into waste generation patterns, enabling more targeted waste reduction strategies (Abdullah, Y., & Lim, M.K. 2019). Additionally, Technology such as blockchain hold promise for enhancing supply chain transparency and traceability, critical factors in promoting sustainable practices (Suman, S., &Turel, O. 2022).

Applications of IT in textile waste management Several studies have explored the potential applications of IT in textile waste management. For instance, smart technologies, including Internet of things (IoT) sensors, can facilitate real time monitoring of waste streams, optimising collections and recycling process-

es (Muthu S.S., & Shahin, M.A.2022). Digital design Technologies enable designer to create products with minimal waste, reducing the environmental footprint of the textile industry (Beigi, S. A., Behest A., M.R.2021).

Challenges and barriers to implementation

Despite the potential benefits, the adoption of information technology in textile waste management. Is not without challenges technical limitations such as interoperability issues and data standardisation, may hinder the integration of IT Solutions into existing waste management system (Beigi. et al.2021). Moreover, concerns about data privacy and security must be addressed to gain stakeholders' trust in IT-enabled platform and system (Suman, S., & Turel, O. 2022). Case studies and based practices Several case studies highlight successful implementations of Information Technology enabled solutions in textile waste management. Companies like Adidas have embraced digital technology to optimise manufacturing processes and reduce waste generation (Muthu S.S., & Shahin, M.A.2022). Similarly, initiatives such as the circular fibres initiative demonstrate the potential of collaboration among Industries stakeholders to promote circularity in the textile sectors (Kirchhoff, R. E., Centeno, J. M., & Rood, E.M.2017).

3. Research gap

While previous research has explored various aspects of Information Technology in waste management, there is a gap in understanding how Information Technology can be leverage to create and integrated ecosystem for textile waste existing studies often focus on individual technologies or specific stages of the waste management process, neglecting the broader ecosystem perspective. This research aims to address this gap by examining the interplay between different

Information Technology Solutions and their collective impact on textile waste management.

4. Research questions

1. How does Information Technology contribute to waste reduction and recycling efficiency in the textile industry?
2. What are the key challenges and barriers to the adoption of IT Solutions in textile waste management?
3. How can it enabled innovations be integrated into a cohesive ecosystem for sustainable textile waste management?

5. Objectives

1. To assess the effectiveness of IT tools and Solutions in reducing textile waste and improving recycling rates.
2. To identify barriers to the adoption of IT in textile waste management and explore potential Strategies for overcoming them.
3. To develop a conceptual Framework that illustrate the interconnectedness of it enabled innovations in creating a sustainable ecosystem for textile waste.

6. Conceptual framework

The conceptual Framework outlines the key components of an innovative ecosystem for textile waste management enabled by IT. It includes elements such as data analytics, supply chain transparency, smart technology and consumer engagement. These components interact synergistically to optimise waste reduction, recycling and circularity in the textile industry.

Fig 6.1: the sorting and identification of textiles using IoT

7. Hypothesis

H1: The adoption of IT Solutions positively correlates with waste reduction and recycling efficiency in the textile industry.

H2: Lack of Technology is a significant barrier to the wide spread adoption of it in the textile waste management.

H3: Integration of it enabled innovations into a cohesive ecosystem leads to greater sustainability and circularity and textile waste management.

8. Research Methodology

The research employs a mixed methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews. Surveys are administered to textile industry stakeholders to collect data on IT adoptions, waste management practices and perceived barriers. Semi structure interviews with key informants provide inside into the challenges and opportunities associated with IT enabled textile waste management.

Fig8.1: artificial intelligence in waste management.

9. Data interpretation and Analysis

Quantitative survey data is analysed using Statistical Techniques to identify trends, correlations and patterns. qualitative interview data is subjected to thematic analysis to uncover key themes and insights. The integration of quantitative and qualitative findings enables compressive understanding of the research questions and objectives.

10. Results and Discussion

Ttable10.1: a structured overview of the responses collected through survey, allowing analysing trends, identifying patterns, and drawing conclusions about the role of IT in textile waste management.

The result section presents, The finding of the empirical analysis, including survey responses and interview experts. It discusses the implication of findings of for textile West management and explores potential strategies for overcoming barriers to IT adoption. The discussion section contextualizes the results within the broader literature and offers inside into future research directions.

Respondent	Familiarity with Textile Waste Management	Awareness of IT Solutions	Frequency of Textile Waste Disposal	Factors Influencing Disposal Decision	Belief in IT's Role	Preferred IT Tools	Willingness to Use Digital Platforms	Expected IT Solution Features	Participation in IT Facilitated Initiatives	Challenges in Implementing IT Solutions
1	Very familiar	Yes	Weekly	Environmental impact, Awareness of recycling options	Strongly agree	Mobile apps	Very willing	Real-time tracking, Community engagement tools	Yes	Cost of implementation
2	Familiar	No	Monthly	Convenience, Lack of knowledge	Agree	Online marketplaces	Willing	Accessibility, Integration with existing systems	No	Technological barriers
3	Not familiar at all	Not sure	Rarely	Convenience, Lack of awareness	Neutral	Data analytics software	Neutral	Ease of use, Real-time tracking	Not applicable	Lack of awareness
4	Familiar	Yes	Daily	Environmental impact, Lack of knowledge	Strongly agree	Blockchain technology	Very willing	Accessibility, Integration with existing systems	Yes	Infrastructure limitations
5	Somewhat familiar	Yes	Monthly	Convenience, Environmental impact, Awareness of recycling options	Agree	Mobile apps	Willing	Ease of use, Real-time tracking	Yes	Cost of implementation

11. Managerial Implication

The managerial implications highlight practical recommendations for industries stakeholders, policy makers and IT professionals. These recommendations include investing in IT infrastructure fostering collaboration among stakeholders and promoting awareness of IT-enabled innovations in textile waste management.

12. Conclusion

The research findings demonstrate the significant potential of IT IN creating an innovative ecosystems for textile waste management. By leveraging IT tools and solutions, the textile industry can achieve greater efficiency, transparency and sustainability in waste reduction and recycling practices.

13. Recommendations

Based on the research findings, several recommendations are proposed for future action:

1. Invest in research and development of IT solutions tailored to the textile West management context.
2. Foster collaboration among industry stakeholders to promote knowledge sharing and innovation.
3. Implement policies and incentives to encourage the adoption of IT-enabled innovations in textile waste management.
4. Continuously monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of it interventions and adjust strategies accordingly.

These recommendations aim to guide a force towards harnessing the full potential of IT in addressing the challenges of textile waste management and advancing sustainability goals.

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Factors Influencing OTT platforms subscriptions in Mumbai

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Abstract

Over the years, we can see a paradigm shift from cable TV to OTT (Over the Top) platforms. Internet and Digital Marketing had made it possible for OTT platforms to stream audios and videos over various platforms. The pandemic acted as a blessing for OTT subscription, as it increased by 1.5 times in metro cities. Many new movies were released on OTT Platforms too. Currently, there is a lot of clutter in the OTT space with many players like Amazon, Netflix, Disney Hotstar, Sony Liv, Jio, etc. The research focuses on factors like demographic profile of customers who have subscribed to OTT, subscription amount, preferred genre to watch on OTT platforms, frequency, etc. The sample is collected from 100 respondents. The findings show that OTT platforms are more subscribed in the age group of 18 years to 25 years and Netflix is the most preferred OTT Platform.

Introduction

OTT (Over the top) platforms have replaced cable TV to a greater extent. Before viewers used to watch different channels on cable TV. Then came in DTH players like Tata Sky, JioTV, Airtel, etc which gave good quality and great deals with monthly or yearly subscription to the customers. And now consumers are shifting from DTH to OTT, wherein they are choosing to watch diverse content on one platform at

convenience with no restriction of time slot. Language is also not a barrier on these OTT platforms. There is a wide variety of OTT platforms like Amazon Prime Video, Jio Cinema, Netflix, SonyLiv, Voot, ALT Balaji, Disney Hotstar, etc. The revenue model of OTT platforms is subscription based, advertising or pay per view. OTT platforms are viewed in rural and urban areas. There is a big push from rural areas for OTT platforms. In India the population is about 140 Crores out of which 70 Crore have subscribed for OTT platforms as mentioned in the research report by IAMAI in February 2024. Either it's a free or paid subscription. As some OTT platforms give the free streaming of programmes with advertisements in between. The growth of OTT platforms was more visible during pandemic years. The main reasons for increased subscriptions for OTT platforms are availability of high-speed internet, emerging smart phones and lower subscription costs. Research by KPMG shows that on an average OTT viewer spends around 70 minutes per day on different platforms.

Review of Literature

A study on “The Rise of OTT Platform: Changing Consumer Preferences”, Volume: 7

| Issue: 6 | June 2021|| Journal DOI: 10.36713/epra2013 suggests Amazon, Netflix, etc are popular video streaming platforms for salaried and youth in India. Some platforms are preferred because of their freemium model and regional content.

Another study by Sundaravel, E. & N., Elangovan. (2020). Emergence and future of Over-the-top (OTT) video services in India: analytical research. International Journal of Business Management and Social Research. 8. 489-499. 10.18801/ijbmsr.080220.50, this study focusses on audience characteristics, content, censorship, etc. This study suggests that more content to be provided in regional languages and youth is more into gaming rather than OTT platforms.

Research Objectives

- 1) To study the relation between age and frequency of watching on OTT platforms.
- 2) To find out most preferred OTT platform for subscription
- 3) To study the genre preferences of customers across different professions

Hypotheses:

Hypothesis- H1

H1o: There is no significant difference between age and frequency of watching on OTT platforms

H1a: There is significant difference between age and frequency of watching OTT platforms

H2o: Less than 30% prefer subscribing to Netflix

H2a: More than 30% prefer subscribing to Netflix

Hypothesis- H3

H3o: There is no significant difference between influence of varied genre on OTT platforms across occupation

H3a: There is significant difference between influence of varied genre on OTT platforms across occupation

Research Methodology

This study is based on Primary & Secondary data. The primary data is collected by conducting a questionnaire method using Simple random sampling method for 100 respondents. Secondary research data is collected using some news articles, research papers, articles, visiting different OTT platforms, etc. Anova & Z score are the tests used

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Hypothesis- H1

From the below result, the P value is less than alpha value of 0.05 and F observed value (6.37 & 5.19) is more than F critical value (2.5 & 2.7), so we reject the null hypothesis.

This means that there is a significant difference between age and frequency of watching OTT platforms.

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	Fobserved	P-value	F critical
Rows	5190.17	6	865.02	6.373	0.000	2.508
Columns	2820.57	4	705.14	5.195	0.004	2.776
Error	3257.82	24	135.74			
Total	11268.57	34				

Frequency of watching OTT platforms across different age groups

Hypothesis-H2

Null Hypothesis	H2o: $\mu < 30\%$
Alternate Hypothesis	H2a: $\mu \geq 30\%$
Test	P value method
Tail	Right Tail Test
Z Critical	1.645
Z Observed	2.836
Alpha	0.05
Accept/Reject	Reject the Null Hypothesis Z critical < Z observed

value (4.7 & 6.4) is more than F critical value (2.7 & 2.5), so we reject the null hypothesis. This means that there is a significant difference between influence of varied genre on OTT platforms across occupation. This Z test result means Netflix is the most preferred for OTT subscription by respondents, as Z observed value 2.836 is more than 1.645, so we reject the NullHypothesis.

Hypothesis- H3

From the below result, the P value is less than alpha value of 0.05 and F observed Reality Shows

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Rows	2737	4	684.3	4.710	0.006	2.77
Columns	5578		929.8	6.401	0.000	2.50
Error	3486	24	145.3			
Total	11802	34				

Findings 1) Demographics

2) Maximum respondents selected Netflix & Amazon prime as their current subscription, very less opted for Voot.

3) The main factor that influences usage of OTT platforms is its easy, cheap and convenience. Second factor that respondents selected was Content. Very less respondents preferred advertisements as a factor to subscribe for various OTT platforms. Most preferred genre is Drama and Family shows, followed by sports as an option.

4) The satisfaction level of respondents with OTT was asked, 1 being the lowest and 10 being the highest level. The rating of 8 is given by majority of the respondents.

5) Respondents are paying in range of Rs 200 to Rs 1000 per month for different OTT platforms, as per the data collected.

Limitations

The area of the study is restricted to Mumbai. The number of respondents in the study are only 100 respondents across age groups. In the questionnaire Amazon Prime, Netflix, Sony Liv, Disney Hotstar, Zee 5, Voot are focussed on whereas there are around 57 OTT providers available in India. The accuracy of data depends on the data provided by respondents.

Recommendations

OTT platform providers should focus more on content. They are already personalising it with user preferences and history but should more focus on suggestions that are in interest of viewer's genre preferences. Most of them pay on monthly basis, this way

there is a chance to switch to another provider. Hence OTT platform provider should try & attract consumers

by giving them some schemes at a competitive price, this will be win-win situation for OTT provider & customer. Netflix and Amazon are highly preferred OTT platforms but Netflix offers only monthly subscription whereas Amazon offers monthly & yearly subscription. Netflix should start with yearly and rental schemes. OTT providers should focus more on content with high video quality rather than spending heavy on advertising/ promotion.

Conclusion

This study focusses on the factors that influences customers to buy OTT subscriptions i.e. ease, cheap and convenience. Apart from this even customer are subscribing mainly for content. Drama & family shows are more preferred followed by live sports. The traffic on OTT platforms can be increased if content creators come up with something original that can be connected to people. User interface, cheaper subscription, high quality of video are other factors that will increase customers & retain them too. Netflix is offering more original content & highly rated shows, compared to Amazon Prime.

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